

The Alan Turing Institute

Reinforcement Learning Study Group Report – February 2021

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Multi-agent reinforcement learning
algorithm performance in
unfamiliar domains

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Contents

1	Challenge overview	3
2	Main objectives	3
3	Learning environment overview	4
3.1	Software implementation	7
3.2	Competitive framework	8
4	Summary of team reports	9
4.1	Robustness Team 1	9
4.2	Robustness Team 2	9
4.3	Transferability Team 1	11
4.4	Transferability Team 2	12
4.5	PI approaches	15
5	Limitations	15
6	Main conclusions	16
7	Recommendations and future work	17
A	Report from Robustness team 1	19
A.1	Approach	19
A.2	Literature Review	20
A.3	Approach	23
A.4	Initial experiments	32
A.5	Report on the competitive phase of the DSG	37
A.6	Findings and limitations	37
A.7	Future work and research avenues	39
A.8	Team members	42
B	Report from Robustness team 2	43
B.1	Summary of Approach	43
B.2	Approach	44
B.3	Initial experiments	56
B.4	Report on the competitive phase of the DSG	57
B.5	Findings and limitations	63

B.6	Future work and research avenues	64
B.7	Team members	65
C	Report from Transferability team 1	67
C.1	Approach	67
C.2	Imitation Learning	68
C.3	Self-Play	71
C.4	Bayesian Optimisation	72
C.5	Guided rewards and reward shaping	75
C.6	Learning to Understand the Observation Space	81
C.7	Report on the competitive phase of the DSG	87
C.8	Findings and limitations	96
C.9	Future work and research avenues	96
C.10	Team members	97
D	Report from Transferability team 2	99
D.1	Approach	99
D.2	Approach	102
D.3	Initial experiments	113
D.4	Report on the competitive phase of the DSG	115
D.5	Findings and limitations	118
D.6	Future work and research avenues	127
D.7	Team members	128
E	Robust Adversarial Approaches	132
E.1	Implementation	133
E.2	Results	133
E.3	Future Work	134
F	Tournament Results	135
F.1	Friday 5 th March	137
F.2	Monday 8 th March	139
F.3	Tuesday 9 th March	140
F.4	Wednesday 10 th March	142
F.5	Thursday 11 th March	144

1 Challenge overview

This document reports on an The Alan Turing Institute Data Study Group (DSG) investigating a Reinforcement Learning (RL) challenge posed by Defence Science and Technology Laboratory (Dstl).

Dstl is “the science inside UK defence and security.” As such, they provide evidence required by Defence to make effective decisions. For example, a planning exercise seeks to optimise the use of available resources to achieve a desired effect. Simulations and games can be helpful tools in answering the required questions.

RL has been shown to be able to generate effective (even super-human) agents to play games such as Go [59, 60] and Starcraft [9]. Dstl would like to investigate RL in the context of games that are relevant in the defence sphere, and in particular whether RL can provide solutions which are adaptable to changes in the configuration of the game. The aim of this DSG is thus to investigate the effectiveness of RL techniques when the rules of the game change between the training phase and the deployment phase.

2 Main objectives

The goal of the study group is to explore the extent to which policies trained using Multi-agent RL algorithms can perform well when confronted with unfamiliar domain parameterisations and new opponents. In particular we seek to compare the performances of agents in two different settings:

1. An (immutable) agent pre-trained with a generalisable policy that encounters a randomly generated environment parameterisation at test time. Robust strategies should be able to perform well, with no further training, across a wide spectrum of game parameters.
2. An agent that is given the test-time parameterisation in advance, with enough time to adjust its policy but not to be trained from scratch. Learning approaches should be devised that facilitate rapid fine tuning of pre-learned strategies.

The first setting is clearly more challenging than the second; we seek to

find out how great this difference is. The main objective of the study group was to discover multi-agent RL approaches that can result in robust or transferable strategies.

3 Learning environment overview

To support this DSG activity, Dstl commissioned Montvieux to create the *Hunting of the Plark (HotP)* Artificial Intelligence (AI) testbed based on the eponymous paper game designed by John Salt at Cranfield University. The HotP is a parameterised, two-player, zero-sum game in which a submarine (the ‘panther’) tries to evade a maritime patrol aircraft (the ‘pelican’). Both players navigate around a discrete hexagonal grid. The panther, starting at a random location on the lower edge of the grid, wins by either reaching the upper edge of the grid or by evading the pelican until the time limit expires. The pelican wins by destroying the panther with a torpedo. The pelican can move around, but cannot see the panther; to detect the panther the pelican has a Magnetic Anomaly Detector (MAD) that will indicate if it has flown within range of panther during its turn; the pelican can also drop sonobuoys that detect whether panther is within range, and can drop torpedoes that destroy the panther if it is within range. The panther can simply move around. The full sets of actions available to the agents are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

In the ‘pure’ form of the game rewards are sparse in that each agent receives +1 for winning the game and -1 for losing, although this can be supplemented with shaped rewards. There are no draws.

Examples of domain parameters in this game include (but are not limited to) the map size, number and speed of torpedoes available to the aircraft, sonobuoy lifetime and range, and the movement capabilities of the two players. Further rules of the game that can change are the ‘bingo limit’ which determines when the panther wins by default because the panther has ran out of fuel and whether the Winchester rule (when the aircraft has dropped all its torpedoes, and all torpedoes in the water have finished running, the panther wins) and escape rule (when the panther starts its turn on the top edge of the map) are in force. The full set of these parameters, and their accepted ranges, are given in Table 3.

Pelican's Actions		
Name	Value	Description
"1"	0	Up ↑
"2"	1	Up Right ↗
"3"	2	Down Right ↘
"4"	3	Down ↓
"5"	4	Down Left ↙
"6"	5	Upper Left ↖
"drop_buoy"	6	Drops a sonobuoy
"drop_torpedo"	7	Drops a torpedo
"end"	8	End turn

Table 1: Set of Pelican actions

Panther's Actions		
Name	Value	Description
"1"	0	Up ↑
"2"	1	Up Right ↗
"3"	2	Down Right ↘
"4"	3	Down ↓
"5"	4	Down Left ↙
"6"	5	Upper Left ↖
"end"	6	End turn

Table 2: Set of Panther actions

	lb	ub
map width	25	35
map height	25	35
maximum turns	25	50
panther move limit per turn	1	3
pelican move limit per turn	15	25
number of torpedos	1	5
number of sonobuoys	15	25
torpedo turns	1	3
torpedo initial speed	2	4
sonobuoy search range	2	4
sonobuoy active range	1	4
bingo limit	50	50
Winchester rule	TRUE	TRUE
escape rule	TRUE	TRUE

Table 3: Lower and upper bounds for the configuration parameters

Note that only the initial speed of the torpedo is set; it is then halved (and rounded to the nearest whole number) in the following turns. Also note that whilst the map width and height used in any given tournament ranged from 25 to 35, it was possible to train agents on maps as small as 10 x 10, and in fact this was encouraged (at least in the first instance) since the game played on a full-size tournament map posed a challenge to naive agents.

This large parameter space (trillions of configurations) is a key feature of the game environment that is of interest to Dstl. Different sets of parameters will affect which strategies are viable, and because of the number of parameters and the wide range over which they can be varied, the space of possible game environment configurations is very large. Agents cannot simply learn optimal strategies for each set of parameters, and so must learn robust strategies that perform well across all parameters, or develop mechanisms to adapt rapidly to a configuration that is presented as a test environment.

3.1 Software implementation

The Github repository that teams were given to work with was `alan-turing-institute/plark_ai_public`, a fork of the Montvieux `plark_ai_public` repository. Among other things, the repository includes three Python modules: `agent-training`, `gym-plark`, and `plark-game`.

The `gym-plark` module contains multiple RL gym environment classes, each providing an initialiser and implementations of gym functions such as `step`, `reset` and `render`. The main difference between these environments is the ‘reward signal’ provided, i.e. how reward allocation is coded within `step()`. Teams were able to modify these environment classes or create custom environments in order to perform further reward shaping, but of the classes provided, `PlarkEnvSparse` offers the simplest reward function, allocating a reward of positive 1 for a win and negative 1 for a loss. Environment classes such as `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeployment` focus on allocating rewards for specific behaviours, ignoring the outcome of the game, whereas `PlarkEnv` provides a more general purpose environment with a multifaceted reward signal.

The `agent-training` module provides some ready-to-use Python scripts and Jupyter notebooks, for example, an implementation of self-play, an implementation of Parallel Nash Memory (PNM) [43, 45] and an implementation of Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolutionary Strategy (CMA-ES) [17] (an Evolutionary Algorithm (EA)).

The `plark-game` module is where the game itself is handled, for example translating an action decision of ‘up’ into a change in the agent’s x and y position variables. The web UI is also handled here, and a folder of JSON files provide configurations of the game’s domain parameters that can be passed to the environment classes.

The environments allow agents to interact with either an image-based description of the game state, or a vector form of the game state with features already extracted. Throughout the study group, participants were instructed to use the vector form, to remove one layer of information processing for the learning algorithms.

Figure 1: Diagram of the docker containers used for our tournament setup. In each contest an environment container was launched, that interacted with panther and pelican containers.

3.2 Competitive framework

The study group participants were split into four teams, with two considering robustness and two considering transferability. Daily competitions were run through the second half of the (two-week) study group. Each group was invited to submit competitive panther and pelican agents into a pool and these were played against each other on two test game environments, with the submissions and results made available to all participants following each competition.

We developed a tournament system that made it easy for teams to submit agents that they had developed in their specialised research and development environments, without the need to deal with dependency issues between agents from different teams or with the environment itself. The tournament system design is shown in 1, and it is available at https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/rl_tournament. For each tournament, teams would submit agents as Docker containers. A central tournament docker hosts the environment and passes observations to and receive actions from the Docker containers of the two competing agents.

The difference between the robustness and the transferability groups was that the latter were informed of the test game parameters three hours in advance of the competition submission deadline each day, and could perform further fine-tuning of their agents in the last three hours. No such information was provided to the robustness groups.

4 Summary of team reports

4.1 Robustness Team 1

Robustness Team 1 (RT1) made a number of interesting discoveries (see Appendix A for the team’s full report). In particular, the team found that PPO agents benefit from using a long short-term memory (LSTM) [24], especially the pelican (Appendix A.4.3). RT1 therefore provides evidence to support a hypothesis that was formulated prior to the DSG: that the pelican would benefit from a memory component, allowing it to keep track of previous locations of the panther, even after the later has moved out of the range of the respective sonobuoy(s).

RT1 also laid the foundation for future research on the HotP, advocating a graph-based reinforcement learning approach where the observation vector is mapped to a graph. Since spatial information plays a crucial role in the HotP, the team explored how to model the environment as a graph and leverage graph neural networks (GNNs) to learn efficient policies. In Appendix A.3.7 RT1 first describes how the graphs are built, then turns to the GNN architecture that was used, and, finally, describe how the extracted features are used as an input to the actor-critic algorithm. RT1 also experimented with randomising the domain parameterisations during training (Appendix A.4.1). However, the PPO agents trained using this approach failed to converge.

RT1 made a number of recommendations for future work, including:

1. exploring state abstraction with hidden parameter block MDPs to address robustness across parameter spaces (Appendix A.4.3);
2. building on their graph-based reinforcement learning foundations;
3. the exploration of automated curriculum learning.

4.2 Robustness Team 2

Robustness Team 2 (RT2)’s approach for obtaining robust agents relied on using Parallel Nash Memory (PNM) [44]. The PNM implementation provided by the PIs was adapted to take into account the varying parameterisation of the environment during training, with the hypothesis

that this will yield better-performing agents at test time. Robustness Team 2's full report can be found in Appendix B.

One of the drawbacks of PNM is its lengthy training time. To expedite this and to improve final performances, RT2 bootstrap the PNM algorithm with pre-trained agents coming from a variety of pre-training approaches alongside other teams' submissions from throughout the competitive phase (see Appendix B.4 for details). This approach requires fewer iterations for the agent to learn and converge towards a good strategy. Pre-trained agents were obtained in two ways:

1. Imitation learning starting with well-behaving rule-based (and custom designed behavioural) agents.
2. Reinforcement Learning training using a customised tournament using Proximal Policy Optimisation with agents ranked using ELO rankings.

RT2's findings can be summarised as follows:

1. Rule-based agents using well-chosen strategies can perform very well.
2. Behaviour cloning results in better performing RL agents compared to random initialisation.
3. ELO ranking as used in the PPO tournament is a good metric for comparing agents' relative performances.
4. Varying the game parameterisations during training is key to achieve robust policies (In contrast to the results reported by RT1).

RT2 also identified a number of limitations. First the team observes that it is challenging to encode rule-based strategies that capture all possible game scenarios. Second, incorporating these agents into the provided PNM implementation was challenging as the initial implementation only accepted agents trained using specific algorithms and packages. Furthermore, they found that computing effective Resource Bounded Best Responses (one of the steps in PNM) is time-expensive. Using pruning of past strategies seems necessary to make PNM computationally tractable. Finally, there was not sufficient computation time to maximise performance in agents from the PPO tournaments.

Suggestions for future work include:

1. Putting a pipeline together to generate strategies via PNM, bootstrapped from pre-trained agents.
2. Incorporate memory into the agents, either through Recurrent Neural Networks or by stacking observations.
3. Investigate the benefits of the relative state representation, and extend to a graph-based approach.
4. Improve the bootstrapping code to allow for better re-use of previous solutions.

4.3 Transferability Team 1

Transferability Team 1 (TL1) investigated four different approaches to tackle the challenge (the full report can be found in Appendix C):

1. Create a set of Rule-Based agents in the single agent domain to achieve a wide variety of strategies.
2. Imitation learning, using the rule-based agents created in the previous step to provide expert trajectories.
3. Curriculum learning, first learning easy tasks and then incrementally increasing complexity in the lessons.
4. Reward-shaping to incorporate domain-knowledge into the environment.

The shaped reward for the Pelican was used as a training strategy for submitting Pelican agents to the competition since the first day. When the parameters were announced, 3 hours before the competition, the known game configurations were used to train the agent for around 1,000 episodes. On the 4th day of the competition the identification and removal of a bottleneck within the HotP framework (See Section 5 for details), allowed TL1 to train their pelican agent for over 35,000 episodes. This increase in training episodes resulted in a significantly improved policy (As seen in Figure 26 in Appendix C).

The team also conducted a valuable experiment to evaluate the

usefulness of normalisation within the domain, comparing agents using raw observations and normalised observations against agents trained on Gaussian noise in place of the environment observation vector. Only the agents trained on the raw environment observations performed as expected, reaching the optimal solution in the “Buoys Lesson” and the best performance in the “Chase Lesson” with a trajectory that suggests performance would continue to improve were this agent trained for longer.

For future work the team outlines an approach using Bayesian Optimisation to guide which agents would be candidates to transfer their performance to new domains and then use PNM to find the optimal strategies from these “similar” agents. The time allocated to retrain before the tournaments on each day would have been used for quickly establishing the most promising pre-trained agents, and then further training them in the target domain. However, due to the lengthy training times TL1 decided to focus their efforts on the approaches listed above.

4.4 Transferability Team 2

For Transferability Team 2 (TL2) the high-level approach taken, with transferability in mind, was to have three phases of training (the team’s full report can be found in Appendix D):

1. The first phase involved training agents from scratch to a ‘reasonable’ level on a fixed configuration of the game.
2. The aim of the second phase was to bootstrap from these baseline agents and train a fleet of agents that were “experts” on a particular game configuration.
3. In phase 3, one of the expert agents would be selected to continue training on the tournament configuration.

Which agent could depend on which of the configurations from phase 2 was closest to the tournament parameters. Alternatively, the entire fleet of expert agents could be passed in as initial agents to a run of PNM. The process of PNM would evaluate these agents against the tournament configuration and set their contribution to the mixed strategy accordingly,

and would therefore implicitly handle the (soft) selection of the best expert(s) for any given parameters.

The selection of configurations on which to train expert agents during phase 2 was based on the sensitivity analysis performed. This is described in section D.2.3. Phase 1 training was itself approached in a number of ways, including:

- reward shaping (section D.2.4),
- use of PNM with initial agents trained from scratch (Appendix D.3.2),
- and self-play.

‘Reasonable’ agents could be defined as agents that were behaving in a way that seemed logical from a human point of view when watching the video outputs, or, in the case of PNM, ‘supported’ agents taken from a strategy profile with a payoff closest to the Nash equilibrium once stabilised (more detail in Appendix D.3.2).

The various methods trialled for reward shaping grew from an iterative process, often by including a new reward scheme, and then realising that the agent found a way of exploiting the rewards without increasing its victory probability in the sparse environment. For example, the pelican using torpedoes with minimal use of sonobuoys in response to a reward for moving close to the panther, or continually dropping sonobuoys in the same place (an illegal move in the full game).

Due to the results that show how the measurement of victory proportion was not reliable with low numbers of evaluation episodes, it is likely that the sensitivity analysis results using `SALib` are also not reliable. However, the initial suggestion is that the numbers of torpedoes and sonobuoys, and the size of the board are important parameters for both agents. This is supported by the results of the stress test.

It was also shown that it is very difficult to train agents across randomised game configurations; this process took too long to converge.

Hyperparameter tuning to maximise the reward suggested that a lower-than-usual discount factor ($\gamma = 0.62$) was optimal. This may be because the rewards were set to be very dense during this tuning; it has not been shown whether this extends to optimising for final victory.

An interesting quirk of the PNM process was early termination when training agents from scratch. This is because it was typical for the pelican to struggle to win at all, especially on larger boards, leading the script to calculate a Nash Equilibrium (NE) with zero payoff to the pelican. It was found that the best method to avoid this was to add a small amount of random noise to the payoff values.

A recurring limitation was a lack of time, for example shorter than required training times, evaluation periods that were not long enough to elicit reliable results, and ceilings on set sizes. The short timescale also meant that various avenues of work were done in parallel as opposed to one feeding into the other, in the way that was intended. For example, the agents trained via reward shaping have not yet been fed as initial agents to PNM, both due to time constraints and due to a mismatch in the back-end deep learning framework used (the implementation of PNM uses the PyTorch implementation of Proximal Policy Optimisation (PPO) from Stable Baselines 3, whereas the work carried out on reward shaping was done with the Tensorflow implementation of PPO from Stable Baselines 2, and therefore integration would require some workarounds).

Below are some more specific limitations discovered by TL2, which can be addressed in future work:

- **Pelican training:** Over-fitting is observed on the behaviour of the panther while using the reward shaping.
- **Hyper parameter tuning:** Due to the limitations of time and computations, the hyperparameter optimisation was carried out with limited objective parameters for the small episode.
- **Sensitivity Analysis:** Due to the limitations of time and computations, we only evaluated the model on a given configuration using only ten episodes.
- **Curriculum Learning:** In the preliminary implementation of multi-stage training, the difficulty of environment configuration is based on limited experiment results and human insight and interpretation.

4.5 PI approaches

The PI's also explored methods to address the challenge, and deployed some simple strategies to stimulate the learning environment.

Simple rule based strategies included *team_test:pelican_agent_bottom_third_buoy*. This agent navigates to the bottom third of the domain, lays out sonobuoys across the width of the map, waits for one to trigger, and then ventures to drop a torpedo in near the detection.

An evolutionary algorithm resulted in the strategy *team_test:pelican_james_ea*, which moves to the bottom of the board and drops a torpedo. This strategy performs well against panthers that attempt to hide in the bottom part of the game board.

The PI's, like some of the participants, used rule-based agents as a starting point for neural network controllers, e.g., via imitation learning or by best responding against them. The PIs obtained two agents using this approach, which performed well in the 10x10 tournament on Thursday (*team_test:panther_rahul_10x10* and *team_test:panther_rahul_10x10*). The agents obtained through this process can also be used to obtain an initial population of agents for PNM-type training.

The final approach taken by the PI's, summarised in Appendix E, was to investigate a recent extension of the robust adversarial reinforcement learning framework that adds additional agents to the learning process to encourage robust learning. This Protagonist Antagonist Induced Regret Environment Design (PAIRED) approach [11] showed promise and merits further attention.

5 Limitations

While deep reinforcement learning has enabled numerous breakthroughs in recent years, results on challenging domains are usually accompanied by lengthy training times and the utilisation of state-of-the-art hardware. For instance, while AlphaGo Zero mastered the game of Go without human data, guidance or domain knowledge, it required three days of training on a machine with four tensor processing units (TPUs) [60]. Such

training times are warranted for training a world beating Go agent. In contrast we hypothesised that within the HotP strong agents would be attainable within a few hours of training (based on the selected ranges for the domain parameterisations, and using non-image observations). However, time constraints were a major obstacle for this DSG, as evident from the report summaries above. For instance, the PIs found that training a best response against one of the rule-based agents took about 2^{20} steps with the default PPO algorithm in stable-baselines3. Meanwhile, to increase the number of PNM iterations, teams were resorting to using 2^{10} training steps per iteration for computing a resource-bounded best response.

In addition to training time, the PIs found that estimating the payoffs of a pair of stochastic-policy agents against each other required roughly 1000 episodes for a good estimate with low variance (taking approximately 10 minutes). To save time teams were reducing evaluations to 25 – 50 episodes. The fact that evaluations merely require forward passes upon entering observations into the policy networks raised questions regarding the efficiency of the HotP implementation. Significant progress was made following a discovery by the PIs on Wednesday morning in the second week of the DSG. The domain was being rendered despite using *non-image* mode – i.e., learning from a low-dimensional vector representation of the game. A ten times speed-up was achieved upon disabling this redundant process. Unfortunately this discovery came too late for teams to take advantage of it, with the last tournament taking place the next day. However, this discovery – and a further review of the code – showed that there is scope for further speeding up the domain. Our next steps are to refactor the code to enable fast training times when using non-image observations. We shall subsequently publish a paper to formally introduce the HotP domain, accompanied by some fully trained baseline agents for a range of domain parameterisations.

6 Main conclusions

Unfortunately, because of the limited training and evaluation time available, the results of the daily tournaments (presented in Section F) are not particularly informative as to which RL approaches are most

promising. What we can see is that implementing simple strategies performed best. For example, *team_test:pelican_agent_bottom_third_buoy* – used in all tournaments from Monday onwards – performed well against the majority of other agents. Meanwhile, *team_test:pelican_james_ea* works well against certain hiding panthers that do not move much (e.g. in the Friday and Monday tournaments). Successful panthers included *team_3:panther_ppo_lstm_v1* (RT1), which employed a simple hiding strategy which did well in the Monday tournament, beating *team_test:pelican_agent_bottom_third_buoy*, the only panther to do so in the 10x10 tournament on Monday.

Overall, the environment showed its potential for research into competitive Reinforcement Learning in a partially observable stochastic game. The HotP provides a benchmarking domain for transfer learning, robust (adversarial) learning and curriculum learning. Our hope is that this domain will be embraced by agent-based communities, in particular those interested in reinforcement learning and evolutionary algorithms.

7 Recommendations and future work

Despite the challenges encountered regarding training the agents, a number of approaches were identified by the teams and PIs that warrant further exploration. For instance Robustness Team 1’s approach of modelling the environment as a graph, and applying a graph neural network to learn embeddings for subsequently training a policy could prove efficient (Section A). Curriculum (Sections A.4.2, C & D) and robust adversarial learning (Section E) were also identified as approaches with a significant amount of potential for this domain. The scalability of PNM meanwhile hinges on being able to gather large number of iterations – and thereby RBBRs – efficiently. Furthermore, lack of development time also meant that the teams could only use a single neural network policy in the tournaments, even if they had trained non-trivial mixtures over policies. The provided code base for the tournaments did not support mixing over policies. We are currently working towards solving PNM bottlenecks with regards to efficiently computing RBBRs, and plan to submit a paper to a conference outlining a novel approach.

Based on our tournament results (provided in Appendix F) there is no clear evidence to support the original hypothesis that transfer learning outperforms robust reinforcement learning approaches. However, given the time constraints and training bottlenecks discussed above, even training good agents on a fixed domain parameterisation (with a large enough map) was challenging enough to account for a significant proportion of teams' work. Dealing with the original challenge is left as future work, which will be much more feasible once the environment has been refactored, and thereby significantly sped up. However, one of the main contributions of this DSG is providing numerous approaches for training agents with transferability and robustness in mind, and a Docker based tournament framework for efficiently evaluating agents without any concerns regarding package dependencies. The most obvious high level recommendation therefore is to take the more promising approaches from this report and deploy them in a less time-constrained fashion to find which ones are worth taking further.

A Report from Robustness team 1

A.1 Approach

We approached the problem with implementations as well as a review of relevant literature. We implemented:

- random environments for robust training
- LSTM-PPO agents
- graph-based observation transformations
- a graph neural network
- reward shaping
- an incomplete state abstraction method

We reviewed:

- state abstraction with hidden parameter block MDPS
- opponent modelling (LOLA and Expert mixtures)
- policy distillation
- automated curriculum generation
- causal meta-reinforcement learning

A.1.1 Key findings

Through our implementations and experiments we found that:

- it is difficult to train the pelican in particular
- a panther strategy of not moving is advantageous in many cases
- recurrent policies improve the performance of the pelican, but not of the panther
- randomisation of the environment parameters stops PPO agents from converging

- the observation matrix can be mapped to a graph for graph neural networks
- our implementation of curriculum learning does not assist training
- our implementation of reward shaping does not improve training

A.1.2 Limitations

Our training time was limited, both due to the compute available and the efficiency of the game code. Because of this, it was not feasible to train all agents to convergence.

Compatibility issues and poor documentation meant that we were unable to work with some software repositories in the timescale of the project.

A.1.3 Recommendations and future work

Based on our experiments and literature review, we identify the following areas of interest for future research:

- state abstraction with hidden parameter block MDPs
- graph neural networks
- automated curriculum learning

Generally we find that our implementations could all benefit from further experimentation.

A.2 Literature Review

Reinforcement learning (RL) has accomplished outstanding results in past 10 years. This has led to a drastic increase in the number of applications (from robotics and gaming to finance and biomedicine) and methods (DQN, Actor-Critic, etc). Recent developments inspired to transfer the perspective of training a single agent to the multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) framework (see the recent survey [22]).

Robust Reinforcement Learning

Key challenge of this study was to address robustness with respect to environment parametrisation.

One of the common techniques is to use a Hidden-parameter Markov Decision Processes (HiPMDP) [12], see Subsection A.4.3. This setting identifies the dynamics of new task instances in several settings, flexibly adapting to task variation. In [48] both dynamics and reward can change as a function of hidden parameters that vary across tasks. However, that approach is limited to the inference of the domain parameters at a test time. In [67] the further extension is proposed by enabling robust state abstractions of Block MDPs.

The other way to go around robustness is to follow a *Curriculum learning* approach, where the complexity of agent's tasks is gradually increased throughout the whole training process [38, 4]. In [49] an agent (adversary) applies destabilising disturbances to the system, whilst the main policy learns to adapt to these scenarios.

Training an agent in a varied environment allows agents to generalise across the variations in the environment[46]. This creates a strategy that is more robust to changes in the environment that it is trained in. Training agents with randomly distributed parameters allows agents to perform well on fixed, randomised and extreme parameters.

In [8] the independent policy gradient methods are run in at a different timescale that in turn guarantees the convergence to the Nash equilibria.

Graph-based Reinforcement Learning

See Subsection A.3.7 for comprehensive overview.

Game theory

The ultimate goal of a game theory is to postulate and find an equilibria with certain properties. Since the seminal work of Nash [42], who formulated his famous notion of the equilibria and proved its existence for certain class of games, a mass body of literature has been developed

together with a growing computational power to support it. Today the equilibrium of a finite game can be computed using one of the algorithms (see [32, 50], etc.). The learning of these algorithms is *Parallel Nash Memory* also known as *Double oracle algorithm*, that was initiated in [39] as a part of the robot learning task.

Meta-Reinforcement Learning

Meta-learning applies the methods of machine learning to the problem of developing a model that can learn new tasks. Where a conventional machine learning task has a set of learning examples to train over and an objective which quantifies the model's performance to be optimised, meta-learning uses a collection of machine learning tasks and optimises for a meta-objective that quantifies how well the model learns on each task. In this way, a model can be trained to "learn to learn", to improve its ability to adapt to new tasks.

Meta-reinforcement learning is the application of meta-learning to reinforcement learning, for the purpose of resolving two key problems in this area: the need for large volumes of training data for agents, and the limited ability of agents to adapt to out-of-distribution tasks. As a result, meta-reinforcement learning is a natural fit for this task, which requires the training of agents that are robust to significant changes in the parameters of the game.

Miscellaneous

One may want to incorporate Environment Similarity technique: [28] presents a method for measuring the similarity between two environments and as well measures how overfitted agents are to a specific environment. Other methods include Opponent modelling and Policy distillation, see Section A.7 for comprehensive overview.

A.3 Approach

A.3.1 Baseline algorithms

We used a Parallel Nash Memory¹ to attempt to determine a baseline for training agents in the environment. We used a PPO training method with a MlpPolicy with the stable baselines3 framework². These agents were trained on the balanced 10×10 configuration of the hunting of the plark. Figure 2 shows the agents begin to converge towards a game value of 0.4 with a support size of 1.

Figure 2: PNM solving the the 10×10 configuration

A.3.2 Summary of approach

The following approaches were trialed to learn robust strategies:

¹https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/plark_ai_public/blob/master/Components/agent-training/agent_training/pnm.py

²<https://github.com/DLR-RM/stable-baselines3>

- Randomised environments
- Parallel Nash Memory
- Curriculum Learning
- Graph Neural Networks
- Reward Shaping
- State abstraction with hidden-parameter block MDPs

A.3.3 Randomised Environment

One approach is to create a new environment that encapsulates the challenge of training an agent to work effectively in an environment with unknown parameters. To do this we create a random environment that uses random parameters every iteration. We use the upper and lower bounds as specified in a configuration file to control the values that parameters may take. This allows us to increase and decrease the randomness in the environment. We aim to train an agent capable of purposefully acting in the random environment and in doing so create an agent robust to bounded changes to the environment. If an agent is able to converge in the random environment against a fixed opponent then that agent has learnt a robust strategy for all potential environments encapsulated by the random environment [46]. We can then extend this challenge to a multi agent challenge that uses the randomised environment that can be solved using methods such as PNM or self play. There is a concern that the randomised environment will be too complex for a basic agent to learn. Changing the parameters in the environment will alter the balance of power between the panther and pelican. The change in parameters may also necessitate vastly different strategies for example spamming torpedoes as the pelican may be effective if the pelican has lots of torpedoes with a large speed, however this strategy would be much worse if the pelican has a single torpedo with a small range.

A.3.4 Parallel Nash Memory

We make use of the *Parallel Nash Memory*(PNM) [43] technique which is also known as the *double oracle* algorithm [39]. This tool allows to compute a mixed Nash equilibria of two-player zero-sum game. Namely, the algorithm solves a set of two-player subgames induced by subsets $\Pi_t \subset \Pi$ at iteration t . The strategies in Π_t are used to construct a payoff matrix of subgame G_t . At each iteration, the algorithm computes a Nash equilibrium σ_t^* of a subgame G and adds the corresponding best responses (as well known as *Resource Bounded Best Responses*) to form a next iteration step, i.e. the subgame G_{t+1} is defined for the new set of strategies Π_{t+1} , where $\Pi_{t+1} := \Pi_t \cup \{\pi'_{t+1}\}$, where $\pi'_{t+1} \in \text{BR}(\sigma_t^*)$. The algorithm stops when the next best responses does not improve the equilibrium from the previous iteration. See [30, Figure 1] for a graphical scheme of the algorithm.

A.3.5 Curriculum Learning

Curriculum Learning refers to gradually increasing the complexity of the task at hand for the agent. This strategy is known to expedite the learning process and improve convergence. However, using a bad curriculum may adversely impact the learning process. Hence, curriculum must carefully be designed.

In the context of the game *Hunting of the Plark*, curriculum can be defined from two components

1. Domain parameters of the environment;
2. Opponent behaviour.

Ideally, we would want to start with environments with small search spaces and easy opponent while gradually increase the complexity of both the components. Moreover, curriculum learning in this scenario is also closely associated with Domain Randomization [62], a technique used to generalise the agents across a wide variations of environments.

A.3.6 Recurrent Policy

The baselines experiments for the game involve the use of *MlpPolicy*. We additionally experiment with the use Recurrent Policies using Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) units in the agents’ parametric policy. This helps encode past states that the agent has seen within the hidden state of the LSTM cells. However, doing so increases the number of parameters the agent has to optimise.

A.3.7 Graph Neural Networks

Since spatial information plays a crucial role in the game, another avenue that we explored was how to model the environment as a graph and leverage graph neural networks (GNNs) to learn efficient policies. In the following, we first describe how the graphs are built, then turn to the GNN architecture that we use, and, finally, describe how the extracted features are used as an input to the actor-critic algorithm.

Encoding observations

We followed two different approaches to turn the observation vectors provided to the agents into graphs.

Grid graph. In our first implementation, the nodes correspond to be the hexagonal cells on the game board, and each pair of adjacent cells is connected by an edge. Each node stores a number of Boolean features: `pelican`, `panther`, `sonobuoy`, and `torpedo` keep track of whether the cell contains, respectively, the Pelican, the Panther, a sonobuoy, or a torpedo. Note that the `panther` feature only applies to the observations provided to the Panther agent, since the Pelican doesn’t have access to the Panther’s location. Moreover, as is suggested by their names, `in_sonobuoy_range` and `in_torpedo_range` indicate whether the cell lies within the range of any sonobuoy or torpedo. Finally, `madman` is true if the Pelican detected the Panther, and `sonobuoy_active` captures information on whether the Panther triggered the sonobuoy within the range of which the cell lies.

Figures 3 and 4 provide a side-by-side comparison of the game board observed by the Pelican and the Panther, respectively, and the

corresponding graph encodings. For the purpose of illustration, the nodes are colour-coded according to their features. Note that only one colour per node is used even when several are relevant—more details on the implementation and plotting can be found in the `GraphBuilder` class in `graphs.py` (for examples, refer to `Building graphs.ipynb`).

Figure 3: **Grid graph (Pelican)**. Pelican's view of the game board (left) and the corresponding graph representation (right).

Figure 4: **Grid graph (Panther)**. Panther's view of the game board (left) and the corresponding graph representation (right).

Information graph. In the second approach, we represented the observations more compactly. Instead of encoding each hexagonal cell

Figure 5: **Information graph (Pelican)**. Pelican’s view of the game board (left) and the corresponding graph representation (right).

as a node, we take as nodes only the cells containing information relevant to the game—that is, the cells containing the Pelican, the Panther, and the cells within the sonobuoy and torpedo ranges. All the nodes are connected to each other to form a complete graph, and a weight is assigned to each edge measuring the grid distance between the two corresponding cells normalised by the maximum possible distance. Similarly to the above, we use five Boolean node attributes, i.e., `pelican`, `panther`, `in_sb_range`, `in_tp_ranger`, and `active`—which is true if the Pelican or the applicable sonobuoy detected the Panther. In addition, we store information about the cell’s location in the hexagonal grid. More specifically, `row` and `col` correspond to the row and the column of the cell, whereby the former is divided by the height and the latter by the width of the game board.

Again, Figures 5 and 6 illustrate how the graphs encode the observations provided to the Pelican and the Panther, respectively. More details are provided in the `SparseGraphBuilder` class in `graphs.py` and the associated Jupyter notebook `Building graphs.ipynb`.

Graph feature extractors

GNNs are effective frameworks to learn graph representations [65, 40]. Typically, representation vectors of individual nodes are learned by

Figure 6: **Information graph (Panther)**. Panther’s view of the game board (left) and the corresponding graph representation (right).

aggregating each node’s own features and the features of the neighbouring nodes. Hence, the resulting feature vectors efficiently capture structural information as well as the distributions of the features of neighbouring nodes. While there are many ways to generate the representations, we primarily focused on the following two approaches.

Graph Isomorphism Network (GIN) was described in [66] to achieve maximum discriminative power among GNNs by generalising the Weisfeiler-Lehman (WL) graph isomorphism test [31].

The model consists of a graph feature extractor and a fully connected classifier (similarly to CNN architectures). Because it can utilise node features and undirected edges, we used it to process the grid graphs described above, which include all hexes as nodes. The corresponding implementation can be found in `models.py`.

However, the same model cannot be used for graphs that additionally include edge labels—such as the information graphs outlined above. To account for this, a different architecture has to be applied.

Message Passing Neural Networks (MPNN) describes a framework in which GNNs can be formulated in a general way. The formalism in [15]

allows the processing of edge labels, which makes this kind of models able to deal with the other type of graph encoding that we propose, namely, the information graphs.

Due to the time constraints, this model was not implemented, but it would be the next logical step to improve the current model.

Actor-critic algorithm

GNNs have already been successfully combined with reinforcement learning approaches in numerous tasks—for instance, to help agents learn to cooperate [25] and coordinate [18], and to optimise traffic routing [2].

In our implementation, which can be found in `policies.py`, we used the actor-critic algorithm, to which we passed the features extracted in the previous step. The actor-critic algorithm provides both an action (actor) and an estimation of the value function (critic). The model is optimised by directly optimising for the expected reward [61].

The model usually consists of a feature extractor, e.g. a CNN for image-based environments, which we exchanged for a GNN. The action and value output is produced by two separate fully connected networks that use the same latent features. The observations that cannot be encoded as a graph (residual observations) are concatenated to the feature map. See Figure 7 for more details.

Our work can be extended in many different ways. One direction would be to explore different GNN architectures [16, 26]. Another would be to implement an additional attention mechanism to account for the fact that most interactions occur locally [34, 35]. Finally, an interesting avenue of research would be to tackle learning more general (symbolic) representations of the environment [14, 29, 58].

A.3.8 Reward Shaping

An approach we use is reward shaping. This is a reinforcement learning technique that improves convergence by providing small rewards for demonstrating successful strategies. This technique is more effective in

Figure 7: Model overview that maps the observations to a selected action and value estimation.

environments with sparse rewards. The risk when using reward shaping is that the minor rewards creates a local optima that a reinforcement learning techniques may find local optima that do not exist in the original game. This leads to the agent learning poor strategies.

Pelican moving to panther

In order to improve the performance of the pelican agent we provide the pelican agent a small reward when it takes an action that moves it towards the panther. This reward is calculated using the true location of the pelican and panther regardless of if the pelican can observe the panther. One one hundredth of the change in Euclidean distance since last turn is provided as a reward to the pelican. This value ensures that the total discounted maximum reward the pelican can receive from moving towards the panther is less than the discounted reward it receives for winning the game. The pelican still receives a reward of '+1' for destroying the panther and a reward of '-1' if the panther wins.

The idea behind this reward is to encourage the pelican to attempt to predict the location of the panther and to move towards that location. Potential issues of this reward is that a pelican may learn to move close but not destroy the panther to get reward. This is especially an issue in games where the torpedo speed is low and must be dropped very close to the panther.

Panther avoiding detection

We also explored how to help the Panther learn to efficiently navigate the game board. We aimed to reward the Panther for successfully avoiding the cells within the detection range of the Pelican or any of its sonobuoys/torpedoes.

To this end, we implemented the `PantherEnvReachTopAvoidPelican` class. It builds upon the `PantherEnvReachTop` class, which encourages the Panther to move towards the top of the board. We extended its framework by adding/subtracting reward depending on the distance between the Panther and the closest cell that would detect it (these are: the cell with the Pelican, the cells upon which the Pelican planted its sonobuoys and torpedoes, and the cells within their detection ranges). Still, to encourage the Panther to wander around and prevent it from getting stuck in a narrow area of the board whilst trying to escape the Pelican, the reward decays with the number of game turns `turn_count`. More specifically, if the Panther triggers any of the sensors (i.e., if the minimum distance to these cells drops to 0), we subtract $1/(\text{turn_count} + 9)$ from the current reward and, analogously, add the same amount if this distance strictly exceeds 1. Note that here—in contrast to the previous section—the distance between a pair of cells corresponds to the smallest number of steps it would take to get from one to the other.

A.4 Initial experiments

Our initial experiments were simple extensions to the existing codebase, with the aim of developing agents that were more robust to changes in the environment parameters.

A.4.1 Randomised Environment

We used a self play script to train the Panther and Pelican against each other in the randomised environment. The Panther was able to quickly find a strategy that consistently defeated the Pelican which resulted in poor strategies for both the Pelican and Panther. Extending this approach to use a league based system may solve this issue, as it would encourage

the development of multiple different strategies.

Another approach could be to alter the game to provide a more effective intermediate score of performance that allows for better measurement of the effectiveness of an agent’s strategy. One example of this would be to reward the panther with how high up the board it can go and provide the negative of that to the pelican. However, this would be complicated by the multiple victory conditions available to the Panther, as waiting at the bottom of the map for the timer to run out is a valid strategy for some environment configurations.

A.4.2 Curriculum Learning

We implement curriculum learning in domain parameters by sampling the environment configuration in every episode We define a curriculum using a schedule based on number of iterations. This schedule decides the distribution from which configurations are sampled. In our implementation, we use the following configurations and schedule and learning setting.

Learning setting:

- Algorithm: PPO;
- Policy: MlpLstmPolicy;
- Agent: Pelican.

Configurations:

- **Balanced:** 10×10 , 20×20 , 30×30 ;
- **Panther-easy:** 10×10 , 20×20 , 30×30 ;
- **Panther-medium:** 10×10 , 20×20 , 30×30 .

Schedule

- Till 200k episodes : uniformly sample from {Panther-easy 10×10 , Panther-easy 20×20 , Panther-easy 30×30 } with weights $\{1, 1, 1\}$ respectively;
- 200k-400k episodes: uniformly sample from {Balanced 10×10 , Panther-easy 10×10 , Balanced 20×20 , Panther-easy 20×20 ,

Figure 8: Learning a single policy for multiple environment configurations, with and without Curriculum Learning.

Balanced 30×30 , Panther-easy 30×30 with weights $\{2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1\}$ respectively;

- 400k-600k episodes: uniformly sample from {Balanced 10×10 , Panther-medium 10×10 , Balanced 20×20 , Panther-medium 20×20 , Balanced 30×30 , Panther-medium 30×30 } with weights $\{1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2\}$ respectively;
- 600k-1000k episodes: uniformly sample from {Balanced 10×10 , Panther-easy 10×10 , Panther-medium 10×10 , Balanced 20×20 , Panther-easy 20×20 , Panther-medium 20×20 , Balanced 30×30 , Panther-easy 30×30 , Panther-medium 30×30 } with weights $\{1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1\}$ respectively.

Figure 8 compares the reward for the pelican agent in two scenarios: 1) random sampling of environment configurations, and 2) using curriculum learning. Through our preliminary experiments we observe that in both the settings, the agent converges to the same sub-optimal policy. This suggests that curriculum in itself is not sufficient in nudging the agent to learn robust policies.

A.4.3 Recurrent Policy

We modify the baseline experiments to use an MlpLstmPolicy instead of MlpPolicy and note the reward in the balanced 10×10 game for both

Figure 9: Rewards over learning iterations for MLP Policy and MLPLstm Policy for Panther agent.

Pelican and Panther agents. Our initial results indicate (see Figure 9, 10) that using recurrent policy is beneficial for the Pelican agent but not so for Panther. Whether this behaviour can be attributed to the specific environment configuration where past states are not relevant for panther or for panthers in general can only be ascertained through further experimentation.

A.4.4 State Abstraction with Hidden Parameter Block MDPs

One potential method to address robustness across parameter spaces in multi-agent reinforcement learning settings makes use of meta-reinforcement learning. For one set of experiments, we defined the problem as state abstraction and encoded it as a Hidden-parameter block Markov decision process as demonstrated by [68]. This approach treats input states as observations that encode to a unique underlying state. The assumption is that every observation maps to a unique state, but a single state maps to multiple observations. The agent then learns the best response with respect to the underlying state, rather than directly from the observations. Given that many observations and game parameters are likely to contain redundant information for the policy, this compression to an underlying state should enable robustness across parameter variations. The distance between observations in state space is computed using the Wasserstein metric.

Figure 10: Rewards over learning iterations for MLP Policy and MLPLstm Policy for Pelican agent.

We implemented an environment that allows interaction between the hunting of the plark game and the `mtrl` codebase³. The `mtrl` codebase is designed for training agents to succeed across multiple tasks due to its use of a state-abstraction [68]. The configuration settings for the hidden parameter block MDP implementation are denoted by `hipbmdp`, and use the Hydra framework⁴. We refer readers to the documentation⁵ for more information. The `mtrl` framework interacts with environments in the `MTEEnv`⁶ format. `MTEEnv` is closely aligned with gym environments, however, the observation space is augmented by task-specific information. This was achieved by wrapping the randomised environment with the `EnvtoMTEEnv`⁷ class, and passing the 15 domain parameters as the task specific observation. Selecting the `hipbmdp` configuration when running `mtrl` learns an embedding of the domain parameters by default. This identification embedding is provided alongside the observation. Unfortunately, due to a dependency on Mujoco, we were unable to complete the implementation of the hidden parameter block MDP framework. We think this could be a useful avenue

³<https://github.com/facebookresearch/mtrl>

⁴<https://github.com/facebookresearch/hydra>

⁵<https://mtrl.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁶<https://github.com/facebookresearch/mtenv/>

⁷https://github.com/facebookresearch/mtenv/blob/main/mtenv/wrappers/env_to_mtenv.py

for future research.

A.5 Report on the competitive phase of the DSG

Each day a set of tournaments with randomly drawn domain parameters were run to measure how good each agent is. All the pelicans were matched up against all the panthers, which resulted in $n_{panthers} \times n_{pelicans}$ matches, each having 50 games.

To provide a ranking between panthers and pelicans we used Trueskill, which is a Bayesian system for rating players' skills [21]. Each player's skill is described by a Gaussian distribution parametrised by the mean μ and deviation σ .

When a match happens with an outcome (win/lose) the belief in the agents' skill gets updated by increasing μ for the winner and decreasing for the loser. The uncertainty decreases for both agents, so σ gets smaller as an agent participates in more matches.

The most useful part of using Trueskill is that each agent group (panthers and pelicans) can be ranked, even though there was no direct match between 2 of the same agent. The ranking of the last tournament can be seen on Fig. 11 and 12. The skill distributions support the intuition that generally the pelicans have a harder task compared to the panthers.

It is important to note, that Trueskill is an online algorithm, i.e. it updates the skill estimates as the matches happen. To accurately capture a snapshot of each agent, it's better to shuffle all the games and updating the skills one game at a time, instead of updating a pair 50 times at once.

A.6 Findings and limitations

Through our implementations and experiments we found that:

- it is difficult to train the pelican in particular
- a panther strategy of not moving is advantageous in many cases
- recurrent policies improve the performance of the pelican, but not of the panther

Figure 11: Trueskill values for each panther in the last tournament (number 85).

Figure 12: Trueskill values for each pelican in the last tournament (number 85).

- randomisation of the environment parameters stops PPO agents from converging
- the observation matrix can be mapped to a graph for graph neural networks
- our implementation of curriculum learning does not assist training
- our implementation of reward shaping does not improve training

A.6.1 Limitations

Our training time was limited, both due to the compute available and the efficiency of the game code. Because of this, it was not feasible to train all agents to convergence.

Compatibility issues and poor documentation meant that we were unable to work with some software repositories in the timescale of the project.

A.7 Future work and research avenues

While the scope for implementation was limited throughout the challenge, a review of relevant literature yielded several approaches that might be of interest to explore at a later stage.

A.7.1 Solving the meta-game

Meta-exploration

Responses to equilibrium strategies computed by PNM will overfit to a specific equilibrium, by on the one hand, having a weak capability for remembering, on the other, limited computational resources. Furthermore, the algorithms will not be able to generalise to the strategies outside of the support of any equilibrium one. This limitations are unwelcome when computing general policies that are expected to be robust to both environment and other player's perturbations. One way of addressing this is to follow the meta-exploration approaches outlined in [30].

Cognitive Hierarchy

Independent learning of the agents is subjected to their beliefs on the opponent actions. As all the agents have different cognitive capabilities, one would expect the high discrepancy between beliefs and the actual performance of the agents in the process of playing. Even replying according to found equilibria may produce a surprising result for the player, as the adversary would not necessarily stick to it. The way to close this bias is to initialise an iterative learning in genre of *Cognitive Hierarchies* as in [6, 30].

Causal Meta-Reinforcement Learning

Another avenue of meta-reinforcement learning uses causal reasoning [7]. The idea is to represent the state-space as a causal Bayesian network, which is explored by interventions. The intervention's effect on the observed variables of the probabilistic network are used by rewarding the agent for correctly predicting the random variable with the highest value. While this method does seem interesting from a theoretical perspective, we see several limitations in practice. This method requires the states to be distilled into a small graphical network. It is not immediately clear how the state or the observation space could be sufficiently simplified to make the method used here immediately viable.

A.7.2 Automatic Curriculum Generation

In our experiments, we tried using a handcrafted curriculum for the agents to learn but it didn't provide any benefits in terms of learning or convergence. We believe it might be better to incorporate learning of curricula in the game's objective itself. Such an approach has been tried for single agent games in works like [52], [33], [10]. Having a similar setup for multi-agent competitive games would be a great direction for future work.

A.7.3 Opponent Modelling

Opponent modelling is of interest in MARL, since it potentially allows agents to infer unobserved information about the other agent. Often in deep learning reinforcement learning implementations, learning the dynamic model of the opponent is considered to be implicit to the learning task. However, the dynamism of the opposing agent, and, with respect to robustness, the potential of being confronted with different opponent strategies from game to game, mean that it is often beneficial to more explicitly account for the opponent. We investigated two different frameworks to account for the opponent.

LOLA - Learning with Opponent Learning Awareness [13]

The LOLA algorithm adapts the update function of the policy gradient descent algorithm to include the effect on the agent's own parameters of the gradient update of the opponent. This stabilises the training of multi-agent environments, and, allows for cooperation in the iterated prisoner's dilemma. A codebase for LOLA exists⁸, as well as for the general higher-order gradient computation algorithm *DICE*. The drawback of LOLA for solving robustness is that it is a training algorithm, and therefore does not provide better generalisability. Potentially the algorithm is more applicable to transferability scenarios, where a pre-trained agent is fine-tuned while taking their opponent's parameter simultaneous parameter updates into account. A further limitation of LOLA arises when the opponent's parameters remain unknown. This is true in most competitive settings, and the proposed solution is to use an maximum likelihood estimate of the opponent's parameters. We note that it is not immediately clear from the results the authors present how successful LOLA with policy estimates is. Furthermore, LOLA is demonstrated for the iterated prisoner's dilemma, a considerably smaller game.

Deep Reinforcement Learning Opponent Modelling with Expert Mixture [19]

This work trains an opponent representation embedding to generate weights for a series of Q-experts. This work appears in some ways analogous to PNM, although the mixture over experts is a weighted average, rather than a mixed strategy distribution. The weight embedding of the opponent is trained with auxiliary supervision in the most successful case, where the target is either the opponent action or the opponent type. A Lua codebase is provided by the authors⁹. Using a weighted average of multiple expert strategies is a form of policy distillation.

⁸<https://github.com/alshedivat/lola>

A.7.4 Policy distillation

We briefly reviewed policy distillation as an option to generate more robust strategies. The benefits we considered were two-fold: 1) policy distillation could be an alternative to the agent mixture distribution for PNM; 2) a policy distilled from a selection of expert policies may prove more robust against a variety of opponents. We identified the following research and codebase¹⁰ as potentially of interest, although we did not explore this further. [63].

A.8 Team members

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Vadim Platonov Vadim Platonov is a third year PhD student at the University of Edinburgh. His research is focused on the mean-field games and stochastic analysis.

Nele Quast - Nele Quast is a 1st year PhD student at the international Max-Planck research school for intelligent systems. Her research focuses on computational Theory of Mind for improved human-computer interaction, to which end she builds multi-agent reinforcement learning models. She contributed a literature review and investigation of meta-reinforcement learning to the project.

Maxwell Standen Maxwell Standen is a researcher in Defence Science and Technology Group (DSTG) in the Department of Defence. His research interests include multi agent reinforcement learning, gym environment development, and the reality gap between simulations and the real world. Max contributed to the random environment implementation, meta-reinforcement learning investigation, and reward shaping exploration sections of the project.

Louie Terill

Shresth Verma Shresth Verma works as a Data Scientist at Optum India, a United HealthGroup Company. He has previously obtained a Master's degree in Information Technology from IIITM Gwalior, India. His thesis work explored the application of reinforcement learning for damage adaptation in robotics and for emergent communication in multi-agent systems. During the Data Study Group, he investigated how sequential modelling through LSTM and domain adaptation using curriculum learning affects the learned policies of agents.

⁹<https://github.com/hhexiy/opponent>

¹⁰<https://github.com/RuohanW/RED>

B Report from Robustness team 2

B.1 Summary of Approach

While the environments used in RL are generally immutable, in this work we are faced with a game whose parameterisation changes (although the rules and objectives remain the same).

To tackle this challenge we use Parallel Nash Memory (PNM) [44], an algorithm that can identify a Nash equilibrium strategy profile for asymmetric games. We have adapted PNM to take into account the varying parameterisation of the environment both during training, which we expect to yield better-performing agents at test time.

One of the drawbacks of PNM is its lengthy training time. To expedite this and to improve final performances, we bootstrap the PNM algorithm with pre-trained agents coming from a variety of pre-training approaches alongside other teams' submissions from throughout the competitive phase (see Section B.4). This approach requires fewer iterations for the agent to learn and converge towards a good strategy.

Our pre-trained agents were obtained in two ways:

- Imitation learning starting with well-behaving rule-based (and custom designed behavioural) agents.
- Reinforcement Learning training using a customised tournament using Proximal Policy Optimisation with agents ranked using ELO rankings.

B.1.1 Key findings

1. Rule-based agents using well-chosen strategies can perform very well.
2. Behaviour cloning results in better performing RL agents compared to random initialisation.
3. ELO ranking as used in the PPO tournament is a good metric for comparing agents' relative performances,

4. Varying the game parameterisations during training is key to achieve robust policies.

B.1.2 Limitations

1. It is challenging to encode rule-based strategies that capture all possible game scenarios.
2. Incorporating these agents into PNM was difficult as the initial implementation only accepted agents trained using specific algorithms and packages.
3. Computing effective Resource Bounded Best Responses (one of the steps in PNM) is challenging and extremely time-expensive. Using some sort of pruning of past strategies seems necessary to make PNM computationally tractable.
4. There was not sufficient computation time to maximise performance in agents from the PPO tournaments.

B.1.3 Recommendations and future work

- Put our whole pipeline together to generate strategies via PNM, bootstrapped from pre-trained agents.
- Incorporate memory into the agents, either through Recurrent Neural Networks or by stacking observations.
- Investigate the benefits of the relative state representation, and extend to a graph-based approach.
- Improve the bootstrapping code to allow for better re-use of previous solutions.

B.2 Approach

B.2.1 Baseline algorithms

Proximal Policy Optimisation We used Proximal Policy Optimisation (PPO) [56] in our RL tournament and when generating the Resource Bounded Best Response (RBBR) in PNM. PPO is suitable for discrete

action spaces and trains a stochastic policy which is required for good performance in stochastic game settings. In addition, the Stable Baselines implementation supports parallel training through the use of vectorised environments, which is possible given PPO is a derivative of Asynchronous Advantage Actor Critic (A2C) [41].

The theory behind PPO is to constrain policy improvement but in a simpler way compared to Trust Region Policy Optimisation (TRPO) which applies a hard constraint on the KL-Divergence between the new and old policies. There are two primary variants of PPO: PPO-penalty which penalises the KL-divergence in the objective function and PPO-clip which clips the objective function to prevent the new policy changing by large amounts during each training iteration. Early stopping also prevents the final policy diverging too far from the initial policy. Stable Baselines implements the simpler PPO-clip which contains no KL constraint or penalty term but has been shown to empirically work just as well as PPO-penalty and TRPO. PPO agents provided a baseline for both the pelican and panther by playing against rule-based agents. This can be extended by playing PPO agents against one another which is discussed further below.

Self-play The logical next step is to carry out self-play to simultaneously train RL agents which can lead to high performance [59]. In this set up the agents adjust their stochastic policy towards the current best response. However, the quality of each player's actions depends critically upon the actions that the other player is likely to take which is constantly changing during self-play. A change in the opponent's strategy will result in the player's own strategy being out of date. In addition, the evaluation of agents trained using self-play is not straight forward as the performance of one of the agents is highly dependent on the opponent's performance. For these reasons, we pursued a Parallel Nash Memory (PNM) strategy which computes an approximate Nash equilibrium using RBBRs which gives a mixed strategy using multiple RL agents.

Parallel Nash Memory We implemented an adaptation of Parallel Nash Memory (PNM) [44], an algorithm for identifying equilibrium mixed strategies in asymmetric two-player zero-sum games. PNM operates by

maintaining sets of stochastic strategies (or policies in the language of RL) S_1 and S_2 for the two players p_1 and p_2 , and builds a payoffs matrix M for the specific sub-game formed by these two sets by playing each strategy $s_{1,i} \in S_1$ for player p_1 against each strategy $s_{2,j} \in S_2$ for p_2 , so that $M_{i,j} = u(s_{1,i}, s_{2,j})$, where $u(\cdot)$ is the payoff function of the game. A linear program (LP) is then constructed from this payoff matrix M and solved for the two players to obtain the equilibrium mixed strategies σ_1 and σ_2 as well as the Nash equilibrium value of the game (for the strategy sets S_1 and S_2). The algorithm then computes best responses BR_1 and BR_2 against the mixed strategies of the opposing player σ_2 and σ_1 , that are then added to the set of strategies S_1 and S_2 , and the algorithm proceeds to the next iteration, until the value of these best responses has converged to the value of the game itself.

We have been provided with an implementation that uses neural networks to represent strategies for the players in this temporally-extended game, and computes resource bounded best responses (RBBR) in the form of training a RL agent against opponents sampled from its mixed strategy for a certain amount of iterations. Payoffs entries are computed by playing games between the two considered agents and taking into account the victory percentage with respect to one of them.

B.2.2 Innovations to address the challenge

Developing prey-predator cybernetic rule-based agents In the Hunting of the Plark, the behaviour of (already developed) rule-based agents followed an open-loop zero-feedback system behaviour. Whereas, in practice more intelligent animals like agents should follow a negative-feedback system behaviour [55]. In order to overcome this behavioural illusion of the predefined agents, new agents were developed using the methods that adopt negative-feedback systems rather than open-loop systems. The behaviour of these newly developed agents is organised around the test of perceptual control variables (TCVs). A more detailed description of TCVs can be found in the literature of Perceptual Control Theory (PCT) [36, 37, 51].

Three new negative-feedback system or PCT agents were developed, while the premise of the agents was that they control their perceptual inputs to achieve their ultimate goals. In the Hunting of the Plark, the

panther plays the role of 'prey' whilst the pelican acts like a 'predator'. The newly developed agents' roles are derived from animal pursuit systems and hence their respective behaviours are consistent with the predator-prey animal pursuit strategies [5, 53]. Different variables of the environment were sensed and transformed into perceptual inputs that were controlled by the agents through their dynamically varying actions [27]. The identification of TCVs were not performed in this project, although it was taken from a similar experimental context, where humans played the role of prey and predator similar to the panther and pelican in the virtual game [55].

For this game environment context, an adaptive cybernetic control strategy was developed for both panther and pelican regardless of the predictability of the movement. One possibility taken into account was that the prey (panther) would attempt to maximise distance where as the predator (pelican) would attempt to minimise distance between their corresponding agents. Hence, panther agents (as prey) controlled their perceptual inputs which maintained a mixture of perceptual distance and protean (erratic evasion) movement strategies, as shown in the figure 13(a)&(b). Whereas the pelican agent having too many parameters at hand, eventually adopted a hunt strategy to minimise the distance between the panther and itself. The predator adopted a search strategy where the space was subdivided into quadrants, while leaving very narrow escape possibilities for the prey, as shown in figure 13(c). That is, the pelican deployed sonobuoys in every quadrant (as a wide range search strategy), and upon activation travels to the towards the target and deploys torpedoes.

Pre-training agents using imitation learning A number of rule-based agents were provided (such as a panther random northerly walk and for the pelican to drop sonobuoys in predetermined locations) in order to provide opponents when training reinforcement learning agents. Furthermore, we handcrafted more complex rule-based agents in order to provide stronger competition to the RL agents to drive the learning process. Pre-training RL agents against rule-based agents provides a baseline performance which can be bootstrapped for enhanced performance in multi-agent settings such as PNM. However, pre-training RL agents against rule-based agents results in the RL agents learning

Figure 13: Rule-based agents - (a) Cybernetic minimum distance (PCT) and protean evasive. (b) Cybernetic maximum distance (PCT) and evasive. (c) Search and attack strategy.

only how to compete against that specific strategy. To realise the full benefit of hand-crafted rule-based agents (which can be very time consuming to create) then a method is needed to distil this knowledge to a neural network policy which can be used in a RL algorithm. One method to do this is imitation learning (IL).

Imitation learning, or learning from demonstrations, assumes access to a dataset of trajectories (state, action, next state tuples), often provided by an 'expert', which can be collected from a human controller or in our case the rule-based agents. A range of learning algorithms exist for exploiting this dataset but the simplest case is behaviour cloning which treats the state-action pairs as independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) and applies supervised learning. Pre-training using behaviour cloning is available as part of the Stable Baselines¹¹ library. The result of

¹¹<https://stable-baselines.readthedocs.io/en/master/guide/pretrain.html>

pre-training is a neural network policy that imitates the expert's actions in a given state and can be used in any policy optimisation RL algorithm. Furthermore, IL is a way to kickstart learning in a sparse reward setting (which the Hunting the Plark game is) as an alternative to reward shaping.

The methodology followed was:

1. Construct rule based agents as mentioned in the previous section.
2. Train a RL agent against the rule based agents to pre-train a neural network policy.
3. Generate expert trajectories by playing a large number of games between the rule based agent and any opponent.
4. Perform behaviour cloning to pre-train a RL neural network policy to imitate the rule based agents.

This process generates two separate neural network policies from a single rule based agent, one of which is trained to oppose the agent and the other to imitate the agent. These pre-trained policies can then be bootstrapped using RL algorithms to improve performance from the rule-based agents. This is shown in figures 14 & 15 which shows superior performing pelican and panther agents after pre-training using behaviour cloning compared to random initialisation of the neural network policies.

PPO Tournament We have seen that training against rule-based agents can yield good results in their respective environments. This approach is however limited due to the finite information contained in such rule based agents, which naturally results in an incomplete exploration of the possible action space.

To improve our algorithm we have introduced a tournament based setting, in which agents are selected randomly to play games against each other and learn from the observed transitions. During training we need to avoid convergence to a deterministic strategy as well as divergence in the training process by training against a quickly changing objective function. For this purpose we fix one agent for a finite number of game steps N , where N is large enough for effective learning, but small enough to avoid

Figure 14: Panther PPO agent training over 10K steps against a rule-based pelican opponent.

learning till convergence. After this training process we make the assumption that the trained agent has now, by random exploration, obtained additional information on how the previously fixed agent can be beaten. We are then able to exploit this additional information in the following step by reversing the roles, fixing the newly trained agent and letting the other agent train. In our experience selecting $N \in [10^3, 5 \times 10^4]$ gave good training results using the default learning rates in `stable-baselines3` implementation of the PPO algorithm.

Translated observation spaces The observation spaces returned by the environment provide our agents with information about the positions of sonobuoys, torpedoes and, in the case of the panther, the position of the opponent. As the environment is hex-grid based all information may be represented by an integer vector:

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{pelican}} \in \mathbb{R}^{109}, \quad \mathbf{x}_{\text{panther}} \in \mathbb{R}^{111}.$$

We believe that an agent that uses the locations of other entities *in relation to itself*, rather than using their absolute locations, will have an advantage during training.

Figure 15: Pelican PPO agent training over 100K steps against a rule-based panther opponent.

As an instructive example we consider two similar game states on different sized maps.

Figure 16: Small environment

Figure 17: Large environment

In both figures 16 and 17 the agents have the same relative position and distance to the lower and right board sides. The agent positions are

however:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pelican}_{\text{small}} &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} & \text{panther}_{\text{small}} &= \begin{pmatrix} 4 \\ 4 \end{pmatrix} \\ \text{pelican}_{\text{large}} &= \begin{pmatrix} 11 \\ 11 \end{pmatrix} & \text{panther}_{\text{large}} &= \begin{pmatrix} 14 \\ 14 \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

In this case the agent trained with relative positions would have two distinct advantages.

First, agents will be able to extrapolate strategies learned on smaller maps to larger maps. In our experiments, as well as in the tournament, we observed that matches played on smaller maps run faster and end sooner. Consequently training agents, especially without reward shaping, is significantly easier on smaller maps. However if absolute positions are used, agents trained on small maps will struggle to translate their strategies to bigger maps at test time. This is because many positions on the map couldn't have been seen during training. On the other hand, if relative positions are used, the only scenarios that the agent would not see during training on a small map are those in which the entities are far apart. These game states are less critical than when the entities are close-by, so not having a good strategy for those situations is less of a problem.

The second advantage lies in the accurate assessment of dangers posed by objects on the map. It is natural to assume that the threat posed by a torpedo to the panther will mainly depend on the distance between panther and torpedo. Relative observation spaces are able to reflect this property naturally. In absolute observation spaces this relationship will need to be learned, increasing required training time and reducing robustness to the map size.

PNM for Robustness We extended PNM, both conceptually and in terms of pure implementation, in various ways to tackle this challenge and achieve robust policies:

- We introduced an occurrence-based pruning mechanism to keep agents' strategy sets small. This sacrifices the perfect recall property of vanilla PNM but speeds up the algorithm execution by avoiding

payoff computation against opponents' strategies that are weak or stale. (In fact we ended up not using pruning for technical reasons.)

- We allow the algorithm to bootstrap from a set of pre-trained agents that do not necessarily need to be of the same type of those trained by PNM.
- We adapted the algorithm structure to use a set of game parameterisations, rather than just a single one, both during training and evaluation:
 - During training, the training process is performed on a sampled subset of the available parameterisations, to allow the trained agent to learn strategies that will perform well in a variety of game configurations.
 - At first, instead of computing a single payoff matrix, we intended to independently compute a different matrix for each available game parameterisation, and the mean of all of these would have been used to solve the LP and compute the agents mixtures. This mean matrix represents 'how good an agent is in general', so using PNM with the mean matrix should yield strategies that are robust against different opponents in different settings.
 - However, we soon found out that this approach was impractical, rendering the execution time extremely long, especially when paired with bootstrapping (and the costs of computing the initial payoff matrices). Therefore, we developed an approximation of the strategy above: we now compute a single payoff matrix, but sample a new game setting to use for each test, so that each strategy is ultimately evaluated against the others on a variety of game parameterisations. So in order to be selected as part of the agent's final mixed strategy, a single 'pure' strategy needs to perform well across different game configurations.

B.2.3 Summary of approach

In this section we describe the pipeline for generating our trained agents.

Figure 18: Overview of the training pipeline used to generate strategies for the panther and pelican.

Ultimately, we use PNM to iteratively train increasingly good agents. In theory we could start PNM with any set of initial agents, but the stronger the initial agents, the fewer iterations will be required. This is important because the running time is quadratic in the number of iterations (because at each time step two new agents are added whose performance must be evaluated against all existing agents).

As such we generate and cherry-pick 'good' agents for the initial pool of PNM strategies. The simplest way of doing this is to create some basic rule-based agents that try to win the game in simple ways (for example a panther that just moves north, or even stays exactly where it is, hoping the pelican will run out of fuel before finding it). By incorporating such agents into the PNM pools we ensure the agents we generate can win against such simplistic strategies. In order to capture the search and predator behaviour of the Pelican and evasion and goal-reaching behaviour of the Panther, we used perceptual control theory (PCT) models of prey-predator pursuits [5, 51, 55]. Consistent with these models rule-based panther and pelican models were developed (as explained in Section B.2.2).

Unfortunately, the initial configuration we used for PNM only accepted agents in the form of policy networks. We therefore used imitation learning to generate agents whose behaviour replicated the rule-based strategies of the agents. A second benefit of imitation learning is that when we train new agents we can bootstrap from the agents that were trained to replicate obviously good rule-based strategies (for example, the panther might want to avoid moving directly towards torpedoes) with the PPO algorithm preventing the policy from diverging too much. Second, we generate agents using a tournament, inspired by [59], as detailed in Section B.2.2.

Finally, a centralised tournament was run each day and other teams' agents were made available. Because both competing agents are being trained, it is difficult to get an objective measure of how 'good' an agent is; the daily tournaments gave an idea of agents' relative goodness and the top-performing agents were fed into our PNM pool.

With all of these strategies as input, Robust PNM iteratively learns best responses so that the panther and pelican strategies it generates are robust against all of the initial pelicans and panthers respectively on a variety of diverse game parameterisations.

Figure 19: Robust PNM BRs value w.r.t. the game value.

B.3 Initial experiments

A large amount of time was spent exploring the code base and running existing algorithms to understand the environment and agent behaviour. The provided code for the Hunting the Plark game deeply integrated the agent within the environment which made understanding the individual components particularly difficult as the agent-environment interface was not clear. This was especially problematic when carryout pure rule-based agent games as the code was constructed in such a way that only Neural Network-based agents were allowed to be the driving player.

Our initial experiments consisted of running the identified baselines algorithms: PPO agents vs rule-based agents, self-play and PNM. Initial findings are summarised below:

- The panther is easier to train than the pelican, even when using the

”balanced” environment settings. This is due to two factors: First, the pelican has a larger action space so it will inevitably take longer to train. Second, the game is set up in such a way that if the agents have not yet been trained to a certain level of ’competence’, the panther will win due to the maximum number of turns elapsing. As such for the pelican to perform well requires a large amount of training time.

- A simple rule-based panther strategy such as staying still, or a random walk north, is surprisingly hard to beat.
- Pelican agents can be taught or learn to place sonobuoys in sensible positions but deploying torpedoes when the sonobuoys are activated is a harder second-order task.
- PNM is very computationally expensive and therefore time spent pre-training RL agents to give them a kickstart is time well spent. Pre-trained agents can be bootstrapped to instil knowledge of the game or pass on sensible strategies rather than training a new agent from scratch.

In hindsight the initial experiments should have also included experimenting with different RL algorithms (we used PPO because it was the default and seemed like a good choice), and we should have performed some simple hyperparameter tuning in order to find the optimal algorithm settings for this context. In addition, more time could have spend evaluating the rule-based agents to ensure the desired behaviour was actually effected when playing the game.

B.4 Report on the competitive phase of the DSG

During the competitive phase of the DSG we submitted agents to a daily tournament, in which they competed against agents submitted by other teams as well as from a central pool.

As the project progressed we refined our approach, and we were able to submit increasingly complex and better-trained agents. Table 4 describes the agents we submitted each day.

In the tournaments our agents enjoyed mixed results. In general our

Day	Agent name	Description
Friday/ Monday	panther_pnm panther_tour1 panther_tour2 pelican_pnm pelican_tour1 pelican_tour2	PNM on 10x10, 50 iterations PPO tournament agent trained for 1h PPO tournament agent trained for 1h PNM on 10x10, 50 iterations PPO tournament agent trained for 1h PPO tournament agent trained for 1h
Tuesday	panther_new1 panther_new2 panther_old1 panther_old2 panther_old3 pelican_new1 pelican_new2 pelican_old1 pelican_old2 pelican_old3	PPO tournament trained on 10x10 and 20x20 maps for 8h PPO tournament trained on 10x10 and 20x20 maps for 8h PPO tournament trained on 10x10 and 20x20 maps for 8h PPO tournament trained on 10x10 and 20x20 maps for 8h PPO tournament trained on 10x10 maps for 8h PPO tournament trained on 10x10 maps for 8h PPO tournament trained on 10x10 maps for 8h
Wednesday	panther_pnm panther_tour panther_imit pelican_pnm pelican_tour pelican_imit	PNM on 10x10, 80 iterations and longer training PPO tournament trained on randomised maps for 8h NN Evasive Manouver (PCT) agent PNM on 10x10, 80 iterations and longer training PPO tournament trained on randomised maps for 8h NN Wide Net agent (PCT)
Thursday	panther_pnm panther_tour panther_imit pelican_pnm pelican_tour pelican_imit	Robust PNM training for 18 iterations PPO tournament trained on randomised maps for 32h NN Danger Clone agent (PCT) Robust PNM training for 18 iterations PPO tournament trained on randomised maps for 32h NN Wide Net (PCT) agent

Table 4: Agents Submitted to the Tournaments

panthers performed well (see figure 21), although this was evident across all teams and suggests one or both of the following, consistent with our initial experiments:

- Training a panther is significantly easier than training a pelican.
- If neither the panther nor the pelican is well-trained (i.e. both follow semi-random policies), the panther will generally win as the game will end before the pelican can sink the panther (due to the maximum number of timesteps elapsing or all torpedoes being exhausted).

We conjecture that both of these hypotheses are true, although we have not fully tested them.

One argument to support these hypotheses can be made by analysing the tournament result data. In Figure 20 we can observe an uptrend in the performance of panthers trained by our PPO tournament. This pattern is seen both on the small 10×10 maps and the larger maps.

Figure 20: Performance of PPO tournament trained agents on different map sizes

We see an increase in panther agent performance, while the same cannot be observed in the pelicans case. This suggests that effective learning in the panthers case has begun, while the pelican agent requires more time. Due to a limited number of samples this analysis cannot allow us to draw any conclusions, but it suggests that the time required to train an effective pelican is greater than for the panther.

We can say that our pelicans generally performed poorly (see figure 22)

during the tournaments. In particular, our pelicans' win proportions on larger grids was invariably lower than on the 10×10 grid, suggesting our agents found it very difficult to generalise to larger maps.

Ultimately, due to the tight time constraints we were unable to pull together our whole pipeline and run PNM with our imitation learning agents, PPO tournament-trained agents, and high-performing opponents from the daily tournaments. As such, any improvement over time has come from refinements to PNM to support robustness and longer training times in the PPO tournament.

Further analysis of the tournament phase is outlined in Section B.5.

Figure 21: Performance of panther agents in tournaments across the week. Our team's agents are highlighted.

B.5 Findings and limitations

We obtained some good insights from our experiments and from analysis of the daily tournament results.

1. Behaviour cloning - using a set of trajectories collected from a rule-based agent to pre-train neural network policies - results in faster-training RL agents compared to random initialisation.
2. Achieving generalisation and robustness in such a setting with so many possible parameterisations is challenging. Given that, we found that randomisation over both the opponent policy and the game configuration is key to tackling this problem. As in our Robust PNM, this randomisation must be performed during the training phase, where agents are trained against varying opponents on different game parameterisations, in order to be robust to changes in the environment at test time.
3. We can observe from the Figures 14 and 15 that learning for the panther is much faster than for the pelican. To achieve observable training improvements for the pelican we required about 10^4 training epochs, with many training samples per epoch. During the PPO tournament only 6×10^4 training samples were generated per agent. These results suggest that effective pelican training in a tournament setting was not feasible due to computational and time constraints.
4. The rules for the rule-based agents can be derived from the behavioural strategies (both for evasion and search) adopted by animals during prey-predator pursuits. These achieved good performance throughout the various tournament that have been held, and thus can serve as a reasonable base to study what to expect from good and general behaviours obtained with RL,

We also identified some limitations to our proposed overall approach, and to the problem framework in general:

1. Due to time constraints we were unable to submit any agents that had been produced by our entire training pipeline; the agents we submitted were only trained by one of the individual components (PPO tournament, PNM or imitation learning).

2. Having very strong agents for behaviour cloning would speed up the agents' training time enormously. However developing and encoding strong strategies in this unfamiliar game was very difficult. Having more sophisticated rule-based agents would allow us to bootstrap much stronger strategies to kickstart our agents' training.
3. Computing effective RBBRs in such a setting with many possible parametrisations is challenging, and computationally demanding. Given the time constraints each of our ideas has not been tested as comprehensively as we would have liked.
4. There was not sufficient computation time to maximise performance in agents from the PPO tournaments.
5. The inability to run image-based algorithms is a limiting factor: we indeed expect that using convolutional neural networks would have been an additional step toward generalisation of results, bringing observations into the same format and flattening the number of domain specific parameters.

B.6 Future work and research avenues

We identified some possible future directions that could yield good results.

- Put together our whole training pipeline. We expect this to produce strong agents that bootstrap from pre-trained agents and learn good strategies from a strong baseline.
- Incorporate some sort of memory (using recurrent neural networks or stacking observations) in the pelican agent (which is affected by partial observability). It seems clear that it would be beneficial to remember, for example, the last known position of the panther revealed by the sonobuoys,
- Other "Cybernetic control" strategies to design better rule-based agents can be taken into account,
- Train the PPO tournament agents for longer.
- More investigation and analysis is needed to understand if and to

what extent the relative state representation can help agents to generalise across different map sizes and game parameterisations,

- More practically, improving the bootstrapping procedure to also be able to work with agents coming from a different version of the Stable Baseline library or trained on a different number of parallel environments would allow us to better re-use previous results and policies.

B.7 Team members

George Watkins is a second year PhD student at the University of Warwick. His research specialism is Relational Reinforcement Learning, with a focus on learning from graph-based states. He contributed to this project as Team Facilitator and adapted the observations so that object locations were relative to the agent's own positions.

Stefan Radic Webster is a second year PhD student at the University of Bristol. His research interests are in reinforcement learning for control of dynamical systems as applied to real world systems. He contribution to the study group by modifying the code to allow rule-based agent games and implementing imitation learning to pre-train neural network policies.

Christoph M. Hoeppeke is a third year PhD student at the university of Oxford. His research is focused on the applications of control theory to accelerated formula one lap-time simulations, as well as reinforcement learning based direct collocation solvers for optimal control problems. He contributed to the study group by implementing a tournament style setting with the ability to train proximal policy optimisation (PPO) algorithms against each other.

Tauseef Gulrez received his Neuroengineering post-doctoral fellowship from Northwestern University, Chicago, and from the University of Salford, Manchester, UK and a Ph.D. in robotics and machine learning (ML) from Macquarie University, Sydney, Australia. He is working as a robotics and AI scientist at Aerospace Division, Defence Science and Technology, Group, Melbourne. His research interests are in developing ML algorithms based on human behavioural strategies. In this group, he developed rule-based agents consistent with the perceptual control theory (PCT) framework of

prey-predator pursuit strategies.

Jacopo Castellini is a fourth-year PhD student at the University of Liverpool. His research mainly focus on learning improved representations for cooperative multi-agent reinforcement learning. His contribution to this project has been the design and implementation of the Robust PNM variant, and he took care of the Docker procedure for agent submission.

Lukasz Pelcner is a first year PhD student at the University of Lancaster. His research mainly focus on model-based reinforcement learning for multi-agent systems in social dilemmas. Contribution to this project has been keeping infrastructure of GitHub, designing of tournament solutions, hyperparameter tuning and training RL agents on VMs.

C Report from Transferability team 1

C.1 Approach

As an overview of our agents, there are four key strategies which form our overall approach to tackle the challenge. More details on these strategies can be found in the following Sections.

1. Create a set of **Rule-Based** agents in the single agent domain to achieve a wide variety of strategies.
2. **Imitation Learning**, using the rule-based agents created in the previous step to provide expert trajectories.
3. **Curriculum Learning**, first learning easy tasks and then incrementally increasing complexity in the lessons.
4. **Reward-Shaping** to incorporate domain-knowledge into the environment.

C.1.1 Key findings

We would suggest first focusing on the Pelican's perspective of the problem, because in the majority of the scenarios, the expected win rate of Panthers is greater than the value for Pelicans. A memory mechanism could be needed to close the gap.

C.1.2 Limitations

Our original approach included Bayesian Optimisation to guide which agents would be candidates to transfer their performance to new domains and then use game theory methods, for instance Parallel Nash Memory, to find the optimal strategies from these "similar" agents. The time allocated to retrain before the tournaments on each day would be then used for quickly establishing the most promising pre-trained agents, and then further training them in the target domain. Given that RL training takes usually long time, in the scale of weeks to months to achieve good results and good single agents are required before we can perform game theory and counter strategies against other strategies we decided to focus our efforts in the steps mentioned in section C.1. Our suggestion is

to maintain multiple events with spread out time for training. In addition, the creation of policies for an environment that was evolving in a parallel fashion to the data study group introduced new tasks in order to maintain compatibility. These factors hindered progress in the limited time frame.

C.1.3 Recommendations and future work

While some results are encouraging, the limitations revealed during the two weeks indicate that more research is needed, particularly to train capable Pelicans able to deal with uncertainty, and where the presence of a memory mechanism would allow the agent to perform in a more goal-oriented fashion.

C.2 Imitation Learning

C.2.1 Baseline algorithms

To train for optimal RL agents in the single agent domain, we tackle the problem using 3 approaches and aim to combine them in the end. These approaches are: imitation learning, curriculum learning, and reward shaping. Given the short time-frame of the challenge, we aim to make use of as many existing libraries as possible.

Heuristic Agents The first step of imitation learning is to have data or experts to learn from. To do this, we implemented several heuristic agents such as “Baby Spice” show in figure 23

The agent goes down to the bottom half of the map - since that is where the Panther is spawning - and places sonobuoys in a simple pattern in the middle area. As soon as any sonobuoy turns hot, the agent will move towards the buoy and drop a torpedo. This agent defeated the random-walk Panther every time we pitted them against each other.

Imitation Learning The motivation of imitation learning is to start the initial policy with expert data. When we tried to train agents from scratch, the agents tend to reach a local maximum and never learn beyond that.

Figure 23: Agent Baby Spice

Our goal is to allow the imitation learner to jump-start the agents exploration outside of this area.

Generative Adversarial Imitation Learning (GAIL) With the recent success of imitation learning using GAIL [23], we attempted to use the GAIL library in stable baselines, we noticed that the documentation states that the data type “MultiDiscrete” is supported, which is the data type our Plank environment uses for observation space. Unfortunately, the code base does not support this observation space and throws an error. We submitted a bug and stable baselines pointed us to use the “Imitation” library, where we found MultiDiscrete is also not supported. We proceeded to modify the code base where it can take our inputs but GAIL throws an error.

Behaviour Cloning With the modified code base, we were able to run behaviour cloning. We generated trajectories and recorded them for use as an expert dataset to pretrain the neural network.

First, we recorded 3000 episodes of expert trajectories and trained a neural network using 128 batch size and 10 epochs for the heuristic agent baby spice. These parameters are also listed in Table 5.

Episodes	Batch size	Epochs
3000	128	10

Table 5: Experimental Settings.

The resulting imitation learning model is meant as an initial policy for the RL learner. It is not, by itself, meant to be an intelligent agent. To show this, we can see that in Figure 24 the imitation model has learned to drop sonobuoys with some separation between them, however the pattern is seemingly more random, and less effective, than the heuristic agent it was trained on (Figure 23). Furthermore, the imitation model has not learned to drop torpedoes near “HOT” sonobuoys. In Figure 24 the Panther is next to the uppermost buoy, but the Pelican remains stuck in the bottom-right corner. This may be because the dropping of torpedoes is far less common in the expert dataset compared to the Pelican’s movement and dropping of sonobuoys. Simply increasing the size of the expert dataset may improve this behaviour, or reweighting trajectories in the dataset according to their rarity could have the same effect.

Figure 24: Baby Spice Imitation Model Behaviour

Heuristic to RL Pipeline We took the behaviour cloned model and trained it on vanilla PPO for 150k steps with the environment standard reward function. The agent does not follow the heuristic agent's original behaviour, but attempts to place sonobuoys in certain areas. It had no trouble finding the Panther (getting hot buoys), but struggles to drop torpedoes in the correct location. As seen in figure 25

Figure 25: Agent Baby Spice with PPO

C.3 Self-Play

We start with training our initial agents on the 10 by 10 balanced grid in two environments: `PlarkEnvSparse` and `PlarkEnvNonImageState`. `PlarkEnvSparse` provides rewards only for winning/losing the game, whereas `PlarkEnvNonImageState` takes into account sonobuoys and illegal moves. We want to understand how much rewards affect the agents' learning. We train our agents with the PPO2 model with 10,000 steps and optimisation of Mlp Policy. Both models have Pelican average reward equal to -1 with 0 standard deviation (sd) in both sparse and non-image environments with 100 evaluation episodes. It is apparent that it is exceedingly harder to train the Pelican agent compared to the Panther.

Can we improve the Pelican agent by considering more ‘sophisticated’ methods like self-play? Self-play starts its training against rule-based agents. If we start with the Pelican we train it against the rule-based Panther. On the next step, the Panther trains against the new Pelican model. It continues like this in the hope to achieve the best-performing agents. As previously, we train our models on the 10 by 10 balanced grid. By default, the self-play implementation in the tournament repository starts with `PlankEnv` for initial agents and switches to the sparse environment after. We run our experiments on these default configurations. Analogously to the previous experiment, we run self-play with PPO2 on the non-image environment. Our parameters are testing interval 1,000, max initial learning steps 50,000, self-play testing interval 1,000, self-play max learning steps per agent 50,000, self-play iterations 50. We provide the results of testing on 100 evaluation episodes for different configuration files in Tables 6, 8, 7, 9. The results indicate that the performance mainly depends on the ‘difficulty’ of the configuration files: the rewards are smaller for the Panther on the Panther easy configurations, etc. However, in the sparse environment, we were not able to train the Pelican agent as the average reward is -1. This experiment shows that ‘sophisticated’ methods would not work unless they are provided with properly designed guided reward functions. We investigate our approaches for the reward shaping in the next sections.

C.4 Bayesian Optimisation

Bayesian Optimisation (BO) builds a probability model of the objective function and uses it to select the most promising hyperparameters to evaluate in the true objective function. The Bayesian approach keeps track of past evaluation results which are then used to form a probabilistic model mapping hyperparameters to a probability of a score on the objective function.

After each evaluation of the objective function, the algorithm updates the probability model (usually given as $p(y|x)$) incorporating the new results. Sequential Model-Based Optimisation (SMBO) methods are a formalisation of Bayesian optimisation that update the probability model sequentially: every evaluation of the objective function with a set of values updates the model with the idea that eventually the model will come to

Configuration File	Pelican reward (sd)	Panther reward (sd)
pelican_very_easy.json	-10.42 (0.5)	-1.0 (0.0)
pelican_medium.json	-14.85 (1.56)	-0.5 (0.87)
pelican_hard.json	-14.85 (1.61)	0.34 (0.94)
pelican_easy.json	-10.5 (0.49)	-0.7 (0.71)
panther_very_easy.json	-15.11 (1.58)	1.0 (0.0)
panther_medium.json	-14.84 (1.61)	-0.78 (0.63)
panther_impossible.json	-14.97 (1.69)	-0.94 (0.34)
panther_hard.json	-15.01 (1.48)	-0.82 (0.57)
panther_easy.json	-14.95 (1.62)	1.0 (0.0)
balanced_max_torps.json	-14.83 (1.73)	0.44 (0.9)
balanced.json	-14.73 (1.53)	0.34 (0.94)

Table 6: Average rewards on PlarkEnvNonImageState of Self-Play PPO2 trained on PlarkEnvSparse

represent the true objective function. The algorithm forms an initial idea of the objective function and updates it with each new piece of evidence.

The next values to try in the objective function are selected by the algorithm optimising the probability model (surrogate function) usually with a criteria known as Expected Improvement. Finding the values that will yield the greatest expected improvement in the surrogate function is much cheaper than evaluating the objective function itself. By choosing the next values based on a model rather than randomly, the hope is that the algorithm will converge to the true best values much quicker. The overall goal is to evaluate the objective function fewer times by spending a little more time choosing the next values. Overall, Bayesian Optimisation and SMBO methods:

- Converge to a lower score of the objective function than random search;
- Require far less time to find the optimum of the objective function.

In the thematic of this project, it was our intention to take advantage of Bayesian Optimisation's efficient sampling mechanism to study the agents' performance across parameters. There are 3 trillion possible

Configuration file	Pelican reward (sd)	Panther reward (sd)
pelican_very_easy.json	-10.41 (0.5)	-0.32 (0.95)
pelican_medium.json	-15.01 (1.6)	0.38 (0.92)
pelican_hard.json	-15.07 (1.57)	0.52 (0.85)
pelican_easy.json	-10.41 (0.5)	0.0 (1.0)
panther_very_easy.json	-14.1 (1.61)	0.64 (0.75)
panther_medium.json	-15.0 (1.39)	0.86 (0.51)
panther_impossible.json	-14.69 (1.66)	0.06 (1.0)
panther_hard.json	-15.0 (1.58)	0.04 (1.0)
panther_easy.json	-13.81 (1.35)	-0.55 (0.87)
balanced_max_torps.json	-14.99 (1.69)	0.7 (0.71)
balanced.json	-15.16 (1.71)	0.78 (0.63)

Table 7: Average rewards on PlarkEnvNonImageState of Self-Play PPO2 trained on PlarkEnvNonImageState

combinations of game configurations, across 15 numerical features. It is impossible to analyse directly the performance of an agent on all combinations, but by evaluating the 15 features as dimensions across a game configuration space, we can interpolate between obtained values and predict unsampled game configurations and its likelihood. By using Gaussian Processes across the 15 dimensions we are able to calculate the uncertainty of the estimates as a proxy of the standard deviation of the Gaussians being fitted across the space. The uncertainty guides the game configuration to be sampled next, to try to minimise the uncertainty across the space.

Finally, by optimising the inverted reward (objectively finding the minimum of the reward across the space), Bayesian Optimisation can efficiently find regions of the game configuration space where the agent underperforms, do a sensitivity analysis where we can say how impactful a specific parameter (considered as a single dimension) is to the agent's performance.

In this two-week project we were not able to apply Bayesian Optimisation to study the agents' performance across game configurations because this method requires an agent that clearly overperforms its adversary. Despite this, we provide the code necessary to run the algorithm for any given

Configuration file	Pelican reward (sd)	Panther reward (sd)
pelican_very_easy.json	-1.0 (0.0)	-1.0 (0.0)
pelican_medium.json	-1.0 (0.0)	-0.62 (0.78)
pelican_hard.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.3 (0.95)
pelican_easy.json	-1.0 (0.0)	-0.68 (0.73)
panther_very_easy.json	-1.0 (0.0)	1.0 (0.0)
panther_medium.json	-1.0 (0.0)	-0.78 (0.63)
panther_impossible.json	-1.0 (0.0)	-0.88 (0.47)
panther_hard.json	-1.0 (0.0)	-0.9 (0.44)
panther_easy.json	-1.0 (0.0)	1.0 (0.0)
balanced_max_torps.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.2 (0.98)
balanced.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.36 (0.93)

Table 8: Average rewards on PlarkEnvSparse of Self-Play PPO2 trained on PlarkEnvSparse

agent to obtain the performance prediction across the game configuration space.

C.5 Guided rewards and reward shaping

The project focused mostly on building strong baseline agents for future training. This effort was largely directed at the Pelican agent as it has the hardest challenge of the two unbalanced adversaries. As an example, a Panther agent whose actions are random would win virtually any confrontations against a Pelican agent whose actions are random. In this section we describe the approach used to shape the reward functions of the agents to mould them towards an effective strategy against a non-trainable adversary.

C.5.1 Pelican

All Pelican agents were trained using Proximal Policy Optimisation (PPO) using the PPO implementation from the `stable-baselines3` Python package. The Pelican agent’s reward was mostly shaped in an ad-hoc fashion to incentivise behaviours that were perceived by the user as

Configuration file	Pelican reward (sd)	Panther reward (sd)
pelican_very_easy.json	-1.0 (0.0)	-0.12 (0.99)
pelican_medium.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.34 (0.94)
pelican_hard.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.42 (0.91)
pelican_easy.json	-1.0 (0.0)	-0.16 (0.99)
panther_very_easy.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.7 (0.71)
panther_medium.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.82 (0.57)
panther_impossible.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.22 (0.98)
panther_hard.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.22 (0.98)
panther_easy.json	-1.0 (0.0)	-0.42 (0.91)
balanced_max_torps.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.82 (0.57)
balanced.json	-1.0 (0.0)	0.7 (0.71)

Table 9: Average rewards on PlarkEnvSparse of Self-Play PPO2 trained on PlarkEnvNonImageState

effective strategies. With a larger set of actions, our goal for the Pelican agent focused on being able to cover the space of its adversaries, while dropping sonobuoys to gain knowledge of the Panther’s location. The provided Random Walk Panther script was always used as the adversary, as its stochasticity makes it impossible for the Pelican agent to exploit a specific path of its adversary (its behaviour is not predictable).

To reward the Pelican movement towards the Pelican, in every agent step the Euclidean distance from the Pelican to the Panther was calculated and stored in the environment memory. If this distance was smaller than the previous iteration, the agent would get a small reward of 0.01, if not it would be penalised in the same proportion. Despite the Pelican agent not knowing the location of the Panther agent, it is able to learn that moving in the lower bounds of the map results in larger rewards. With the same mindset, we also calculated at every agent step the distance from the agent’s position to its position 5 steps prior and 2 steps prior. If the distance towards its position 2 steps prior was smaller than 5 steps prior, the agent would receive a small reward (0.01); if not, it would be penalised. The goal was to keep the Panther moving along the board and to not fixate on a specific position or corner.

One observed behaviour from the agents trying to avoid committing illegal

moves (fomented by its penalisation) is that the agents avoid dropping sonobuoys altogether (dropping sonobuoys in the same location triggers an illegal move and subsequently a penalised reward). To incentivise the dropping of sonobuoys, the environment records how many were deployed and at the end of the episode, the agent is returned a reward proportional to the number of sonobuoys dropped. This way, the agent does not benefit from dropping the sonobuoys early in the episode as the reward is not compounded.

The guided reward for the Pelican was used as a training strategy for submitting Pelican agents to the competition since the first day - Friday the 5th. When the parameters were known, 3 hours before the competition, the known game configurations were used to train the agent for around 1,000 episodes. With the speed up of the process allowed in the 4th day of the competition, the Pelican agent was trained for over 35,000 episodes instead. This was the first time that the agent seemed to reach a saturation of the reward exploitation as seen in Figure 26.

C.5.2 Panther

Although the team's efforts were mostly directed towards training Pelican agents, some time was also devoted to developing Panthers. Our group hypothesised that, for a number of reasons, training a good Panther agent should be easier than training a good Pelican one. Firstly, the Panther has full knowledge of the observation space; in other words, it can see the full game board with buoys and torpedoes, as well as the location of the Pelican. Secondly, the Panther has fewer available actions. This should allow it to make informed choices after a shorter amount of exploration time than the Pelican.

Unfortunately, due to bugs related to saving and loading models, it was not until towards the end of the Study Group that a somewhat intelligent and robust Panther was trained. The reward function for this Panther agent can be seen in Table 10. Note the simplicity of this reward function: the Panther is given a small reward every time it moves up the board, and a much larger reward for winning by 'ESCAPE'; it receives no reward for winning by other means, and is never penalised. The rewards were designed in this way to encourage the Panther to move quickly up the board and pursue an 'ESCAPE' - a reasonable and competitive strategy -

Figure 26: Reward across episodes of a Pelican agent while training using reward shaping. The reward is averaged along a sliding window of 20 values to facilitate interpretation.

rather than winning by ‘BINGO’ (Pelican out of fuel) or ‘WINCHESTER’ (all torpedoes spent). Aside from the reward function, the training environment was a vanilla `PlarkEnv`, with vector-based observations normalised using the provided normalisation function.

Following the approach described above, our group did succeed in training a Panther that essentially moved northwards regardless of the board configuration. This Panther agent, similarly to the Pelican agents that we trained, used the PPO implementation from the

Action	Reward
Panther moves N, NE or NW	0.1
Panther wins by ESCAPE	5

Table 10: A description of the Panther’s reward function.

Parameter	Value
Learning rate	0.0003
Batch size	64
Gamma	0.99
GAE lambda	0.95
Clipping parameter	0.2

Table 11: The default parameters used by the PPO model.

`stable-baselines3` package in Python. The PPO parameters that we used were the default ones. These are shown in Table 11.

The Panther was trained on a game board configured using the `10x10/balanced.json` file that was provided. In this setup, the Panther plays against the heuristic agent `Pelican_Agent_3_Buoys` which has a move limit of 5 (compared to the Panther’s limit of 1 move per turn), as well as 5 torpedoes and 10 sonobuoys available. Full details of this configuration can be found in the `PlarkAI` repository. We chose to randomise the Panther start position during training to aid exploration and to prevent over-fitting to the initial configuration.

After training for 100,000 iterations, our Panther had a win rate of 0.724 over 1,000 games played in the same environment in which it was trained. Moreover, the strategy learned by the Panther was the expected one - in the training environment, the Panther attempted to run more or less directly to the top of the game board. This tells us that that our Panther agent was able to use its reward function in order to learn a good strategy for the game. A plot of the episode rewards during training (with a moving average) can be seen in Figure 27. In addition to recording the episode rewards, the model was evaluated (in an identical environment) over 5 games against the Pelican agent every 1,000 steps. A graph of these results can be seen in Figure 28.

Our Panther agent was also able to perform relatively well in unseen game configurations, without any additional training. We played 1,000 games with a variety of different parameters, and against several different heuristic agents. The results of these experiments are recorded in Table 12. The Panther’s win rate in the training environment is also included as the first entry for comparison.

Figure 27: Panther agent episode rewards during training.

Configuration	Win rate
10x10/balanced.json	0.724
10x10/balanced_pelicanAgent_any_size_grid.json	0.351
10x10/balanced_max_torps.json	0.733
20x20/balanced.json	0.693
20x20/panther_hard.json	0.580
30x30/balanced.json	0.920
30x30/panther_hard.json	0.912

Table 12: Panther agent performance in different environment configurations (with no additional training).

These results show promise for training Panther agents to win by ‘ESCAPE’. In all but one case the Panther is able to win the majority of games. Note that the win rate on the 30x30 boards is so large because the opponent in these cases, Pelican_Agent_3_Buoys, is not optimised for larger board configurations.

Having trained this baseline agent, given a new board configuration, we can use transfer learning to quickly train an agent to fine tune its strategy to a new environment. This was the approach used when training the Panthers for the final tournament (see Section C.7.5 for more details).

Figure 28: Panther agent evaluated in environment while training.

Our next steps in terms of training Panther agents would be to experiment with reward shaping, as well as changes to the observation space. Although the ‘go north’ strategy is a reasonable one, it is not robust to the most skilful Pelican agents. Ideally, we would train a Panther to have an awareness of the Pelican’s location and the positions of sonobuoys so that it could avoid both as it moves up the board, or decide to hide if the ‘go north’ strategy were not feasible. Training this behaviour would require careful tuning of the reward function: too complex and the Panther would be unable to learn the map between behaviours and rewards, but too simple and the desired behaviour could never be achieved.

Furthermore, this reward shaping approach relies on the Panther being able to effectively interpret the observations that it receives. We believe that, with the observation space and normalisation in its current state, the Panther is able to understand very little of its environment. This is discussed more comprehensively in Section C.6.

C.6 Learning to Understand the Observation Space

The behaviour of our trained agents leads us to hypothesise that they struggle to interpret the observation space: they behave as if they can’t “see” the environment. The custom rewards that our agents are most

successful at exploiting each offer a relatively direct relationship between an action and a reward e.g. “move south and you are rewarded”, “drop a buoy and you are rewarded”. Moving from these basic tasks to a relatively simple problem that requires an interpretation of the board state - e.g. “move towards an active sonobuoy”, “drop buoys across the width of the board” - the trained agents struggle to develop a useful strategy.

For example:

- **Models punished for illegal moves** tended to move in a general direction that maximises the distance from their start position to the furthest edge of the board; for example, agents that start towards the top left would tend to move towards the bottom right. They didn't seem to develop any strategies that reliably detect the edge of the board (though some agents would “slow down” when they reach the farthest edge). None of the agents we've trained seemed to confidently explore the board space without making a large number of illegal moves. Those agents that did explore only did so in a very small space of the board, resembling a random selection of one of the six directional moves.
- **Models trained to drop non-overlapping buoys** tended to move directly downward dropping buoys at random intervals. As with illegal moves above, this maximises the space before reaching edge of the board; space in which to drop non-overlapping buoys. The models that achieved the highest scores on this task still frequently dropped buoys that overlapped, suggesting they had not learned to interpret the position of the other buoys, or indeed the current board position of the Pelican. It appears they had simply learned an optimal ratio of moving south and dropping buoys, without any memory of the previous move. Attempts to force the agent to drop buoys across the width of the board from a central starting position were largely unsuccessful.

The common characteristic of these behaviours is that they can be defined by a simple “stochastic strategy”: at each turn selecting from one of the available moves, assigning greater probabilities to the selection moves that result in generally higher rewards. Such a strategy does not require any interpretation of the game state, indeed it is entirely independent of it! This interpretation of our agent's policies is supported when forcing agents to

select moves in a deterministic manner - always selecting the move with the highest probability of maximising the agent's advantage: they always choose the same move throughout the game without adjustment.

C.6.1 Testing “Blind” Agents

To test this hypothesis more rigorously, we created an environment with an option to return Gaussian noise in place of the environment observation vector. We then repeated a number of our initial experiments, replacing the actual environment observations with random noise. Such agents were dubbed “blind agents” given their inability to “see” a representation of the game state. The expectation was that, if our trained agents were learning a representation of the game state from the environment observations, they would behave very differently to “blind” agents, and in particular would achieve much higher rewards.

The results from these experiments are too numerous to report in their entirety, given that we tested many of our previously trained agents using random noise vectors. For the sake of brevity, we limit the reported results to those from the following experimental methods, chosen as they offer some reward for very simple strategies, but a greater maximum reward if an agent develops and “understanding” of the board state to better exploit the environment.

All agents were trained using the `Stable Baselines 3` Pytorch Proximal Policy Optimisation model, with default hyperparameters for 100,000 steps. Each agent was a Panther trained in the “20x20 Panther easy” configuration, in environments with shaped rewards detailed in figure 13.

Agents were given one of three possible configurations of the observation vector (the third, non-normalised, option was added at the suggestion of the principal investigators):

1. Normalised observations (the default normalisation method for the plark environment at the time of writing)
2. Non-normalised observations
3. Random noise

Action	Reward
“Buoys Lesson”:	
Drop buoy	1
If drop buoy:	
Columns to nearest buoy == 2	-1/3
Columns to nearest buoy == 1	-2/3
Buoy in same column	-1
Dropped all buoys (5)	2 (at game end)
“Chase Lesson”:	
End turn	-0.01
Move closer to plark	0.01
Move closer to hot sonobuoy	0.1
Directly over Panther	0.1
Drop torpedo within 5 spaces of Panther	0.5
Win game	1
Lose game	-1

Table 13: A description of the reward functions used to test random noise observations.

C.6.2 Results and Conclusions

Results of the blind agent tests can be seen in Figure 29 and Figure 30. In both experiments, the agents trained using the normalised observations perform worse than those trained on random noise. Only the agents trained on the raw environment observations performed as we would expect, reaching the optimal solution in the “Buoy Lesson” and the best performance in the “Chase Lesson” with a trajectory that suggests performance would continue to improve were this agent trained for longer.

Figure 29: Progression of episode rewards for agents trained using the “Buoy Lesson” environment. In this configuration, the blind agent episodes were considerably longer (proceeded for many more turns before ending) than those of the other agents, thus the number of episodes completed in 100000 training steps is considerably less. It is unclear why this is the case.

These results suggest there are significant issues with the normalised observations. Given that we used these normalised observations in all of our experiments, it is likely these issues are the most significant contributor to the poor performance we have seen. It is not immediately apparent why this should be the case - despite containing a complete

Figure 30: Progression of episode rewards for agent trained using the “Chase Lesson” environment.

picture of the environment, agents don’t appear to be able to parse any useful information from the normalised vectors - indeed it appears these observations act to harm performance or “understanding” of the environment. Given more time we would have liked to investigate this further.

The performance of the blind agents also highlights problematic assumptions that were made in our earlier experiments, and that could be made again in future - namely that agents able to exploit a given reward function are doing so by “understanding” the game environment. Given that blind agents can replicate the performance of agents that can “see”, it must be concluded that many of the policies we have seen that are able to exploit simple reward functions, do so independently of the environment observations. These findings should be taken into consideration if one aims to design guided rewards that encourage an “understanding” of the game environment - one must ensure that any promising results can’t be replicated by a simple stochastic or “blind” strategy.

C.7 Report on the competitive phase of the DSG

In the competitive phase, each team submitted their best Pelican and Panther agents for a daily tournament that took part for five day. In this tournament, agents of different teams played against each other, and against baseline agents. Each game between two agents resulted in a win, lose, or draw. Since good policies in the game are stochastic, multiple games were played between each pair of competing agents and the win rate was reported. A final tournament also took place at the end of the challenge.

The following sections present the results for each tournament day, using TrueSkill [20] as a rating system that quantified in a Bayesian fashion the skill of our agents.

C.7.1 Tournaments Day 1

On Day 1, there were two different grid sizes, 10x10 and 25x25. We submitted three Pelican agents: `pelican_latest`, which was an agent trained from scratch on the 25x25 game configuration with reward shaping as described in Section C.5.1 for 1578 episodes; `pelican_pedroTwo` which was trained using curriculum learning, by using an agent trained on a 30x30 game configuration as a starting point for training using our guided reward for 890 episodes; and `pelican_zoe`, which had issues during training and was unable to compete in the tournament.

C.7.2 Tournaments Day 2

On Day 2, there was one grid size, 26x33. Our Pelican agents were generated as following: `pelican_pedroScratch` was trained from scratch on the guided reward mentioned in Section C.5.1 for 861 episodes; `pelican_pedroContinuum` was trained using as a starting point the agent trained on 30x30 grid and the guided reward for 823 episodes.

Figure 31: Day 1: Panthers True Skill on 10x10 board

Figure 32: Day 1: Panthers True Skill on 25x25 board

Figure 33: Day 1: Pelicans True Skill on 10x10 board

Figure 34: Day 1: Pelicans True Skill on 25x25 board

C.7.3 Tournaments Day 3

On Day 3, there were two different grid sizes, 10x10 and 28x26. Baby Spice, the imitation learning Pelican agent with no additional RL

Figure 35: Day 2: Panthers True Skill on 26x33 board

Figure 36: Day 2: Pelicans True Skill on 26x33 board

training, performed surprisingly well in the tournament. The true skill [20] shown below in figure 37 and 38 shows it only lags behind the heuristic agents on a 28x26 size board. And behind the heuristic agents and an

evolutionary algorithm agent on the 10x10 size board.

Figure 37: Agent Baby Spice True Skill on 10x10 board

Figure 38: Agent Baby Spice True Skill on 28x26 board

Figure 39: Tournament results in a grid of 25 x 25

C.7.4 Tournaments Day 4

On Day 4, there were two different grid sizes, 10x10 and 28x28.

Scary Spice, the imitation learning Pelican agent with 3000 sample episodes with 150k steps of PPO training, performed relatively poorly compared to Baby Spice, as seen in Figures 41 and 40.

Old Spice was an agent trained with guided rewards for 972 episodes and using as initial point the Baby Spice agent previously trained through imitation learning. Okish Spice was trained trained from scratch for 1000 episodes and Salty Spice was trained from scratch for 3596 episodes, both on the same guided reward. From the results it's possible to infer that the larger number of steps did lead to a stronger agent and that the Salty spice agent seemed to reach a reward plateau as shown in Figure 26. This was the first tournament submission that took advantage of the training speed-up, allowing for the first time to train more than 1000 episodes in the allocated time.

C.7.5 Tournaments Day 5

On Day 5, there were two different grid sizes: 10x10 and 28x25.

Pelican agents Two Pelican agents were submitted Pelican_pedro_small and Pelican_pedro_large. Pelican_pedro_large was trained from scratch using our guided reward for 3509 episodes on the game configuration with the larger grid (28x25). Pelican_pedro_small was trained from scratch in the smaller 10x10 map, for 2,791 episodes. They were respectively optimised for each of the two grid sizes and their result reflect as such: they present good

Figure 40: Tournament results in a grid of 28 x 28

results in the game configurations on which they were trained, and bad results otherwise.

Panther agents Due to issues with saving and loading agents using the methods from `stable-baselines3`, this was the first day on which well-trained Panther agents were submitted to the tournament. Both agents utilised the reward function described in Section C.5.2, but were trained on a number of different board configurations and against different opponents.

- **mowgli**: Our first Panther, `mowgli`, was designed to perform well in the 10x10 tournament. The baseline agent for this model was the Panther trained on the `10x10/balanced.json` configuration described in Section C.5.2. We then trained this agent for 30,000 iterations against `Pelican_Agent_Any_Size` using the first 10x10 configuration provided for the tournament, labelled '00', but randomising the Panther's position at the start of each episode. Finally we trained this agent with each of the 10x10 tournament configurations in series, against a `Pelican_Agent_3_Buoys` opponent and for 10,000 steps each.

Figure 41: Tournament results in a grid of 10 x 10

- bagheera:** The other Panther that we submitted to the Day 5 tournament was trained to perform well in the larger 28x25 environment. The baseline for this agent was a Panther trained for 60,000 steps against Pelican_Agent_Any_Size on the 28x26 '00' configuration from the Day 3 tournament, with the Panther's start position randomised. We then trained for 100,000 steps, once again against Pelican_Agent_Any_Size and randomising the Panther's starting position, but this time in the 28x25 '00' configuration for the Day 5 tournament. Finally, we attempted to train for 10,000 steps per given 28x25 configuration. We played against Pelican_Agent_Any_Size in half of these, and Pelican_Agent_3_Buoys in the other. Due to time constraints, we had to finish training after 186,000 of the desired 240,000 steps.

Both of these Panther agents performed well in the Day 5 tournaments. A summary of their performance can be found in Table 14. Note that here a 'battle' consists of multiple 'games', and the win rate is calculated across games as opposed to battles. As we would expect, `mowgli` is the stronger agent on the 10x10 grid, and `bagheera` the stronger when faced with the 28x25 configuration.

Agent	Grid size	Battles won	Battles drawn	Battles lost	Win rate
mowgli	10x10	13	0	1	0.88
mowgli	28x25	12	0	1	0.89
bagheera	10x10	12	1	1	0.83
bagheera	28x25	13	0	0	0.97

Table 14: Performance of our team’s Panther agents in the Day 5 tournaments.

Day	Pelican	Panther
Day 1 (March 5)	pelican_latest pelican_zoe pelican_pedroTwo	panther_zoe
Day 2 (March 8)	pelican_pedroContinuum pelican_pedroScratch	panther_zoeMonday
Day 3 (March 9)	pelican_babyspice	panther_zoe_small panther_zoe_large
Day 4 (March 10)	pelican_okish_spice pelican_old_spice pelican_scary_spice pelican_salty_spice	panther_blind
Day 5 (March 11)	pelican_pedro_small pelican_pedro_large	panther_mowgli panther_bagheera

Table 15
Tournament Submissions Team 1

C.7.6 Summary of submissions

The agents submitted each day to the tournament performed by Panther agents are provided in Table 15.

Figure 42: Tournament 4 (Grid 25 x 25)

C.8 Findings and limitations

Given our time, using RL libraries such as OpenAI stable baselines was a must, implementing our own algorithms simply takes too long and we cannot guarantee the training speed performance to finish in time. Therefore, we relied on the implementations of the libraries, we noticed that if the library had unfinished implementations or bugs, we would not get the feature we wanted to try in time for the tournament.

C.9 Future work and research avenues

Because of the partial observability of the Pelican, we think that there is potential to exploit RL algorithms that handle such cases better. For instance, Counter Factual Regret Minimisation (CFR) [69] can be helpful in improving the agent performance in similar problems.

Another potential research path is the use of memory in the Pelican, for instance Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) that would allow to handle the temporal features of this challenge, and link it with the MARL problem. For instance, a work that could be useful is Spatio-Temporal Multi Agent Reinforcement Learning [64], which could also be potentially linked with the graph representation introduced by the team facing the robustness

challenge.

Some of the aims of this hackathon involved trying to estimate the value of the game for a particular configuration and being able to train a Resource-Bounded Best Response (RBBR) to a particular strategy. However, due to the difficulties we had in training a good single agent, we were unable to tackle any of the multi-agent problems. Further advances in the performance of single agents would allow further study into the game-theory and multi-agent aspects of the game.

One of the robustness teams used a knowledge graph to represent the states to learn generality, one of my projects is collaborating with the group that developed novelty handling agents [47], where they generalise the observation space with natural language words and therefore learns on a more general description of the game, independent of the parameters. Changes will be found on the knowledge graph and the RL agent will then retrain from the last best policy using transfer learning. Expanding on this work in Plark is another avenue of future work.

Finally, another approach for the Pelican is to use a neural symbolic reasoner to learn to reason the Panther location based on evidence in the observations. And choose torpedo placement location based on the symbolic reasoning.

C.10 Team members

James Chao is a war gaming AI researcher at Naval Information Warfare Center Pacific (NIWC PAC). With experience in RL, planning, evolution, and reasoning AI, along with past experience on war game AI such as Hunting of the Plark while collaborating with DSTL and DSTG. James contributed to this project with heuristic and imitation learning agents, while sharing many past lessons learned on RL and Plark.

Pedro F da Costa is a PhD Researcher in Machine Learning applied to Neurosciences at King's College London and Birkbeck College. In his research he is using concepts of AutoML, Bayesian Optimization and Deep Learning to build tools to optimize for presented stimuli in neuroscientific research in human-in-the-loop approaches and to build anomaly detection systems for psychiatric data using normative models.

Raisa Dzhamtyrova is a research associate at The Alan Turing Institute working on risks for the project of Trustworthy digital identity systems. She did her PhD in online machine learning at Royal Holloway, University of London. She contributed to the project by training agents with the Self-Play approach and evaluating it on different grid configurations.

Christopher McNicol works at the Maritime Warfare Centre (MWC), conducting Operational Analysis and developing battle-winning tactics for the Royal Navy. He contributed to this project by creating heuristic agents and using these for imitation learning.

Sam Relins is an intern Data Scientist at the Leeds Institute for Data Analytics (LIDA) - his work at LIDA centres on predictive modelling in paediatric healthcare and birth cohort settings. He contributed to this project by developing guided rewards and curriculum strategies to train the Panther agent, given the additional complexity of the Panther role.

Omar Verduga is a PhD candidate in Experimental Psychology at the Queen Mary, University of London. In his academic research, he is focusing on computational models of human decision-making in dynamic environments. He also has collaborated with the DSTL programming experiments on visualising dynamic uncertainty. His role on the Data Study Group team has been group facilitator.

D Report from Transferability team 2

D.1 Approach

The high-level approach taken by the team, with transferability in mind, was to have 3 phases of training. The first phase involved training agents from scratch to a 'reasonable' level on a fixed configuration of the game. The aim of the second phase was to bootstrap from these baseline agents and train a fleet of agents that were "experts" on a particular game configuration. In phase 3, one of the expert agents would be selected to continue training on the tournament configuration. Which agent could depend on which of the configurations from phase 2 was closest to the tournament parameters. Alternatively, the entire fleet of expert agents could be passed in as initial agents to a run of PNM. The process of PNM would evaluate these agents against the tournament configuration and set their contribution to the mixed strategy accordingly, and would therefore implicitly handle the (soft) selection of the best expert(s) for any given parameters.

The selection of configurations on which to train expert agents during phase 2 was based on the sensitivity analysis performed. This is described in section D.2.3. Phase 1 training was itself approached in a number of ways, including reward shaping (section D.2.4), use of PNM with initial agents trained from scratch (section D.3.2), and use of self-play. 'Reasonable' agents could be defined as agents that were behaving in a way that seemed logical from a human point of view when watching the video outputs, or, in the case of PNM, 'supported' agents taken from a strategy profile with a payoff closest to the Nash equilibrium once stabilised (more detail in section D.3.2).

D.1.1 Key findings

The various methods trialled for reward shaping grew from an iterative process, often by including a new reward scheme, and then realising that the agent found a way of exploiting the rewards without increasing its victory probability in the sparse environment. For example, the pelican using torpedos with minimal use of sonobuoys in response to a reward for moving close to the panther, or continually dropping sonobuoys in the

same place (an illegal move in the full game).

Due to the results that show how the measurement of victory proportion was not reliable with low numbers of evaluation episodes, it is likely that the sensitivity analysis results using `SALib` are also not reliable. However, the initial suggestion is that the numbers of torpedos and sonobuoys, and the size of the board, and important parameters for both agents. This is supported by the results of the stress test.

It was also shown that it is very difficult to train agents across randomised game configurations; this process took too long to converge.

Hyperparameter tuning to maximise the reward suggested that a lower-than-usual discount factor ($\gamma = 0.62$) was optimal. This may be because the rewards were set to be very dense during this tuning; it has not been shown whether this extends to optimising for final victory.

An interesting quirk of the PNM process was early termination when training agents from scratch. This is because it was typical for the pelican to struggle to win at all, especially on larger boards, leading the script to calculate a NE with zero payoff to the pelican. It was found that the best method to avoid this was to add a small amount of random noise to the payoff values.

D.1.2 Limitations

A recurring limitation of the work discussed in this report is lack of time, for example shorter than required training times, evaluation periods that were not long enough to elicit reliable results, and ceilings on set sizes. The short timescale also meant that various avenues of work were done in parallel as opposed to one feeding into the other, in the way that was intended. For example, the agents trained via reward shaping have not yet been fed as initial agents to PNM, both due to time constraints and due to a mismatch in the back-end deep learning framework used (the implementation of PNM uses the PyTorch implementation of PPO from Stable Baselines 3, whereas the work carried out on reward shaping was done with the Tensorflow implementation of PPO from Stable Baselines 2, and therefore integration would require some workarounds).

Below are some more specific found limitations, which can be addressed

in future work.

Pelican training . Over-fitting is observed in the behaviour of the panther while using the reward shaping.

Hyper parameter tuning . Due to the limitations of time and computations, the hyperparameter optimisation was carried out with limited objective parameters for the small episode.

Sensitivity Analysis . Due to the limitations of time and computations, we only evaluated the model on a given configuration using only ten episodes.

Curriculum Learning . In the preliminary implementation of multi-stage training, the difficulty of environment configuration is based on limited experiment results and human insight and interpretation.

D.1.3 Recommendations and future work

As discussed above, there were several avenues that would have benefited from more time.

To address the issue of over-fitting to the panther's strategies, the pelican could be trained against a varying set of panther policies. Further hyperparameter tuning could have been done using different objectives and for longer training times. The sensitivity analysis could have been done using more evaluation episodes to get more accurate results, and compared with the results of the stress test. They could also have been used to guide curriculum training, and incrementally increase the challenge presented by the game configuration.

The high-level plan was to then use the results of the sensitivity analysis to train expert agents on specific game configurations, and then investigate how best to use those experts once the tournament configuration was known - whether to select an agent that was trained on a similar configuration, or to use the whole fleet in a run of PNM.

D.2 Approach

Baseline algorithms During the DSG, the algorithm used was PPO, as implemented in the stable-baselines toolbox. This toolbox has 2 versions of PPO, using either the `PyTorch` or `TensorFlow` libraries. Although there is no discernible difference between these versions, it was found that the provided PNM script (see below) only accepted the `PyTorch` version.

The majority of the training was done using the default parameters in the stable-baselines algorithm, however the hyperparameters were later optimised using the OPTUNA [1] library (see section D.2.2 for more details).

Two training schema were also provided in the repository: self-play and PNM. Self-play iteratively trains the agents against one another, creating an automatic curriculum as the challenge to each agent increases as its opponent improves its performance. This can work very well, but may suffer from over-fitting. To avoid this, PNM retains a set of agents of each kind, which may use completely different strategies. During each round of training, an opponent is selected with probability proportional to its evaluated performance. This method can be slow and expensive if agents are trained from scratch, but can be improved by including either (semi-)trained or rule-based agents in the initial set.

D.2.1 Training Across Domain Parameters

The high-level approach to targeting transferability is to pre-train agents and then, when the target domain is provided, these agents can provide a basis for bootstrapping, receiving the restricted amount of training on the target domain in a way that can be regarded as policy fine-tuning. One approach to the pre-training of these agents would be to pre-train on one specific configuration of the game, and to do this for multiple specific configurations, with some strategy for choosing the best candidate for bootstrapping once the target configuration is released. Further discussion of this approach later in the report refers to these pre-trained agents as 'experts'. Another approach is to have the pre-trained agent experience many types of domain parameters such that it has general strategy across domains - an attractive idea since it provides robustness as a base.

This second approach in itself can be achieved in a multitude of ways. Discussed below are methods that involve using the PNM architecture to provide diverse experience (section D.2.1), and some preliminary work on using multi-stage training, commonly referred to as curriculum learning, to provide diverse experience sequentially (section D.2.1).

Using PNM If an agent can learn different policies under different game configurations, these policies can form a mixed strategy profile that can be evaluated against a target configuration.

Figure 43 shows two strategies that can be applied to training with random domain parameters: a) complete randomness for each model and every iteration; b) randomness across iterations.

Figure 43: Model Training with random domain parameters, two strategies.

Figure 43a shows the model training diagram under such context. For every iteration, each model is assigned with an environment of random domain parameters. During one iteration, the model is trained to be an expert on its own environment and is evaluated against other models on a new common game configuration, which is also randomly chosen. This type of randomness may lead to a longer training process due to the models are hard to find to point to converge. One reason is that there are too many combination of domain parameters, such that models are re-adapting each time. When the models are trained for a long time, they may forget what have been learnt long ago.

Figure 43b shows an alternative solution for training with random domain

parameters. Instead of different environment for each model, the game configuration is unified at each iteration. The environment is only changed where enough mix-strategy training is performed. This approach can ease the burden of re-adaptation for each model by switching between different set of domain parameters more gradually.

Training models with random domain parameters may not work for PNM under a game theorem setting. We aware that NE may not be the same across different domain parameters, so that it becomes difficult to determine the convergence point for the models. The theory on payoff convergence may not be applied, since this iterative training process does not tell us anything about the overall equilibrium point.

Addressing PNM Collapse When we want to train weak agents against strong ones, we often encounter the situation when stronger agents win all the time. This raises a difficulty for any game theory-based training to obtain a mix-strategy. A typical example is shown in Figure 44 where PNM training stops at iteration 4 with pelican as the “weak” agent. The model is far from good since the pelican never wins and receiving negative rewards.

Although rate of victory is a simple and straight forward evaluation for payoffs, it contains the least information on how well the agents perform against opponents. It is usually harder for agents without full information (pelican) to win against agents with full information (panther). This phenomena is strengthened when the game board becomes larger. As a result, the computation of NE fails to find the true value. This can be mainly attributed to the local equilibrium. The model fails to explore more on the possibility to find a global equilibrium. To resolve this issue, we can have two categories of approach: 1) using more informative payoffs; 2) improving algorithm on initial learning stage.

We can use evaluated rewards of policy as more more informative payoffs. Even when the rate of victory is zero or one, the reward values (assuming dense reward) contains more information on the progress of training and how good a model is regard to the rewards. For example, if we give panther reward to go north and give pelican guided reward to capture the panther, the increase in average evaluated reward indicate that the model is fitting more accurately toward the reward shaping. Reward values have the same

Figure 45: Model training with multi-stage.

D.2.2 Hyper-parameter Tuning

Hyper-parameter tuning has always been an essential but dirty part of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). A proper set of hyper-parameters can benefit both model accuracy and speed of training. We deployed a hyper-parameter tuning framework called OPTUNA [1] to maximize the reward of PPO by setting the parameters summarised in Table 16 as to be optimized through 5 episodes with 1000 at each episode.

PPO para	Default Value	Optimized Value
Discount factor	0.99	0.6195
Gae lambda	0.95	0.9160
Clip Range	0.2	0.8286
Ent Coef	0	0.4741
Vf Coef	0.5	0.6432
Max grad norm	0.5	0.2090

Table 16: Summary of hyperparameter of PPO tuned by OPTUNA.

To evaluate the effectiveness, we carried out a comparison experiment on 10×10 balanced using PNM from scratch over 30 PNM iterations, where, at each iterations, the networks was trained 100 training steps with 7 environments in parallel, sampling 28 opponents in total. In Fig. 46a, PPO is trained with the default hyper-parameters, while in Fig. 46b, PPO is trained with hyperparameters optimised by OPTUNA over the training. The comparison of these two figures indicates that the optimised PPO contributes to make the blue line (NE_{payoff}) stabilise quicker under same environmental setup.

a: PPO_{default}

b: $PPO_{\text{optimised}}$

Figure 46: Comparison of the convergence rate in pay off value with (Fig. 46a) and without optimisation on hyper-parameter on PPO (Fig. 46b)

D.2.3 Sensitivity analysis

In phase 2 of the 3-phase plan, agents are trained to be experts on a particular game configuration. In a world of infinite compute power, an expert agent would be trained for every possible combination of parameters. In the real world, it is necessary to intelligently select a only a handful of configurations.

We performed two types of sensitivity analysis:

- A *what-if* analysis by shifting the parameter variable by one unit. This was done using the SALib library [57]. In mathematical terms, the first order sensitivity will be:

$$\frac{\partial f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + h, \dots)}{\partial x_i} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + h, \dots) - f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots)}{h}$$

where x_i are the parameters of the game and $h = 1$. This is described in section D.2.3.

- A *stress-test* analysis shifting the parameter variable by its max range. This was performed using the *bump and re-eval* methodology. It allows us to capture the function's convexity. In mathematical terms, the first order sensitivity will be:

$$\frac{\partial f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + h_{max}, \dots)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i + h_{max}, \dots) - f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots)}{h_{max}}$$

where $(x_i + h_{max})$ is the maximum value of the parameter of interest. These details are given in section D.2.3.

SALib computations In order to understand how to segment the huge parameter space, the SALib [57] was used to calculate the sensitivity of the agent's performance to each of 11 key parameter variables given in table 3.

Initially, the starting positions of the panther and pelican were also included in the analysis, but they were then removed as the tournament

configurations randomised these. All other possible variables (eg BINGO limit) were kept constant. The same pre-trained panther and pelican agents were used throughout.

SALib generates a sample of parameter values using the lower and upper bounds provided, and the `saltelli.sample(dict)` function. Unfortunately, the parameters it outputs are floats, and so must be converted to `numpy` floats before being used as a game configuration. This may incur some inaccuracies in the sensitivity results. The number of parameter sets generated depends on N , a value input by the user, and D , the number of model inputs (11 here). The output matrix has dimensions $[D, N(D + 2)]$. With N set to 100, 1300 parameter sets were tested.

Using code provided in the repository, the set of parameters produced by SALib was saved into $N(D + 2)$ individual configuration files. The `helper` module's `check_victory(model, env, num_trials)` function was used to evaluate each agent against the other in each game configuration. The number of trials was set to 10. The constraint on computation time limits this to a low value, meaning that the results will be noisy. This is discussed in section D.2.3.

SALib's `sobol.analyze(dict, outputs)` function returns first and second order sensitivities. These were calculated for the pelican and panther victory proportions in turn.

Bump and Re-eval Stress Test analysis Since the policy function is a highly non-linear function on the domain's parameters, sensitivities calculated in an incremental way yield limited predicting power in the change of the policy performance for each game configuration. In a Taylor expansion, sensitivities are only valid on a very local point and cannot be extrapolated further up from its value. For this reason, for variables with a high range of variability, an incremental bump in the variable is of limited use and a full bump has more predictive power. By bumping all the variables to their maximum value we avoid the locality of the Taylor expansion and are able to account for the convexity of the function.

Utilisation of sensitivities The question is then how to use the sensitivities, once they have been calculated?

Small, medium, large The first option is simply to select the (say) 6 most important parameters (determined by their totalled sensitivity values), and vary each of these to (say) 2 values: small and large, whilst keeping the other parameters at midpoints.

This has the benefit of being easy to match to a tournament configuration, by considering the deviation of each parameter from its midpoint. If, for example, the number of sonobuoys was the furthest below its midpoint in the tournament configuration, then the expert model selected would be the one that had been trained on the "small sonobuoys" configuration. Dividing the domain parameter space in this way would lead to a fleet of expert agents that would have been trained on one of 12 configurations.

Quadrants Could each of the second-order effects be turned into a quadrant of configurations? For example, see table 17. Doing this for the top 3 pairs would lead to 12 different configurations.

	small width	large width
small pel moves	1	2
large pel moves	3	4

Table 17: Quadrant example

When selecting the expert agent to train further on the tournament configuration, it would be necessary to classify according to two parameters at a time.

Classifying a tournament configuration An example tournament configuration¹² is given in table 18, along with the proportional deviation of each parameter from the midpoint, relative to that midpoint.

The largest deviation is the default number of torpedos. Therefore, if one of the expert configurations has a high number of default torpedos, that

¹²Tournament 2 from Monday the 8th March

parameter	value	dev
map width	26	0.133
map height	33	0.100
turns	50	0.316
moves panther	2	0.000
moves pelican	15	0.250
torpedos	5	0.667
sonobuoys	25	0.250
torpedo turns	3	0.500
torpedo speed	4	0.333
torpedo search range	3	0.000
sonobuoy active	4	0.333

Table 18: Example tournament configuration

expert agent would be used to continue training using this tournament configuration. If not, then the agent trained on the baseline configuration, with all the parameters set to the midpoints, would be used. If a quadrant set of configurations that included the number of torpedos had been used to train an expert agent, then the second parameter in that quadrant pair would also have to be considered.

Variation in victories There are multiple reasons for variation in the outcome of any individual episode, including the randomisation of the starting positions, the inherent stochasticity of the PPO policy, etc. Inaccuracies in the performance of the agents (as measured by the victory proportion in `helper.check_victory(model, env, num_trials)`) will lead to inaccuracies in the sensitivity analysis, potentially rendering that analysis meaningless.

In order to investigate the severity of the variation, a set of trials was run using the same agent and same game configuration. First, `check_victory` was run 100 times with `num_trials` set to 10; then it was run 3 times with `num_trials` set to 1000. This allowed the standard deviations to be measured, and the proportional variance with respect to the 3 1000-run values of each of the 10-run values to be calculated, that is, for each 100-run value, X_{100}^i and each 1000-run value, X_{1000}^j , the proportional deviation

is defined as:

$$\Delta_{i,j} = \frac{|X_{100}^i - X_{100}^j|}{X_{100}^j} \quad (1)$$

giving a total of 300 values, which can be averaged across the X_{100}^i values, or both. Alternatively, the proportional variance in the 100-run values could be calculated with respect to their mean.

Additionally, 20 runs of `check_victory` with `num_runs` set to 10, 50, 100, 150, and 200 were performed, to consider how quickly the inaccuracy changes with the number of episodes considered.

D.2.4 Schedule of reward shaping environments

To improve the speed and convergence of the PNM, we wanted to start with an initial pool of agents that demonstrated a variety of intuitive strategies. We investigated using a schedule of reward shaping environments to bootstrap these initial agents.

As mentioned previously, the `gym-plark` package provided the `PlarkEnvSparse` environment (an environment with a simple, sparse reward signal of plus 1 for a win and negative 1 for a loss) and a few other environments (with simple but targeted reward functions). We started with using a schedule of the existing reward shaping environments, then included modified reward shaping behaviours to address deficiencies that were found.

The input to this training process is a list of environments for the panther agent, a list of environments for the pelican agent, and a game configuration. We first generated a new panther agent, trained the panther in the first environment in its list against the default pelican agent listed in the game configuration. We then generated a new pelican agent, trained the pelican in the first environment in its list against the panther agent in the previous stage. We then alternated between training the panther agent and pelican agent in the next environment in its list against the agent output by the previous stage.

To better understand the behaviour of the agents, videos of 10 games between the agents were output after each stage of training. Observing

the deficiencies in the behaviour of the agents guided changes to the list of environments as well as the game configuration.

The agents were implemented as the `MlpPolicy` provided by stable baselines and trained by PPO.

D.3 Initial experiments

D.3.1 PNM initial pool size constraints

We performed a series of timing measurements to evaluate the constraints on using PNM for the transferability challenge. One possible approach was to use a large pool of initial agents, trained on different configurations, evaluated on the tournament configuration as a base point for training new agents using PNM . Starting from an initial pool of 53 panther agents and 53 pelican agents, we found that for the default game configuration with a 10×10 board the initial evaluation process took approximately 11 hours, which corresponds to the evaluation of each pair of agents requiring 14 seconds to play 25 games. A new agent was trained for the PNM pool in approximately 2-8 minutes; this varied between panther or pelican and whether the training started from random or from an existing agent. With the new agent trained, approximately 25 minutes was required to evaluate the new agent against the existing agents in the pool, which corresponds to the approximately 50 agents multiplied by the 14 seconds per pair multiplied by 2 (panther and pelican).

Restricting the initial evaluation time to 1 hour, to allow the remaining 1-2 hours for training additional agents for the PNM , would allow us a pool of only 16 agents per player in this configuration.

Some alternative approaches that work within the timing constraint include:

- using a small initial pool of robust agents, possibly performing some training of the agents on the specific game configuration before the initial evaluation for PNM .
- rather than completing the full evaluation, only evaluate a subset of pairs of agents and use heuristics to prune poor performing agents

(for example, using a trueskills or ELO ranking system).

D.3.2 PNM trained from scratch

Figure 47: Training progress for a baseline agent

Before transferring into a larger map and more challenging domain parameters, we would like to obtain a strong agent as a baseline agent by training it in a balanced domain parameter using PNM from scratch. In our zero-sum game setup, the **baseline agent** can also act as a reasonable range of initial parameters in a more challenging domain parameter to avoid the initial success rate being dominated by either panther or pelican.

Therefore, we deployed PNM to train the agent in the 10×10 balanced domain parameter from scratch for 100 PNM iterations, where the networks was trained by 100 training steps with 7 environments in parallel, sampling 28 opponents in total. In the PNM, PPO with Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) policy was used as the policy network. The results in Fig. 47 show that

the $NE_{\text{pay off}}$ stabilized around 54 iterations, which is used as the **Baseline Agent** for the mixed strategy and multi-stage training.

D.3.3 PNM bootstrapping from pretrained models

When transferring the model from training environment to tournament environment, we utilize the pretrained models to bootstrap PNM training. In this experiment, two models are used as the initial models for PNM: 1) PNM model trained from scratch under 10x10 balanced game configuration; 2) PNM model trained with tournament configurations with initial model from scratch.

Later, we transferred the model with 10 training steps with 7 environments in parallel, sampling 14 opponents in total. In the PNM, PPO with MLP policy was used as the policy network. The results in Figure 48 shows reasonable behaviour where the pelican payoff stays above NE line and the panther payoff stays below NE line.

D.4 Report on the competitive phase of the DSG

Table 19: Tournament training detail

	Tag	Payoff	PPO	Initial Agents	Iter	Normalized
1	*_pnm_long	origin	default	From scratch	0	TRUE
1	*_pnm_mix	origin	default	pnm_long	7	TRUE
2	*_pnm_mix	reward	default	pretrained	5	TRUE
4	*_pnm_10x10_wed	+ noise	default	pretrained	10	TRUE
5	*_pnm_28x25_thu	+ noise	optimized	sensitivity	2	FALSE

D.4.1 Tournament 1

During tournament 1, we submitted two pairs of models as in Table 19. The first pair (tagged pelican_pnm_long, panther_pnm_long) were the outcome of the original PNM run with default parameters, a 10x10 balanced configuration, and with initial agents trained from scratch (section D.3.2). After we observed the convergence of PNM model at 50-60 runs as in Figure 49. We picked the model according to the support

Figure 48: Bootstrap under 10x10 game board

number of the model and how closely it converged to NE. We first selected models with the highest and second highest support number. Among these models, we chose a pair of models with payoffs closest to NE. Hence, we picked the best model on the 54th run.

The second pair (tagged `pelican_pnm_mix`, `panther_pnm_mix`) were trained using PNM with `pnm_long` as the initial models. Since a set of tournament configurations had been provided, it was possible to provide the agents with experience of the tournament domain parameters by training, for 7 iterations, on a random configuration from that given set.

D.4.2 Tournament 2

In preparation for tournament 2, we used several models as baseline models for PNM training, including the `pnm_long` model from tournament

Figure 49: PNM model with default parameters as baseline agent

1 and self-play models trained with `PlarkEnvSparse`, `PlarkEnv` and `PlarkEnvGuided` reward functions under default parameters. All baseline models were trained on the 10x10 balanced configuration. To avoid the problem where the pelican has a difficult time learning a winning strategy from the beginning (when the win rate is zero), we use `avg_reward` as the payoff, as discussed in section D.2.1. Improving the reward means agents will have higher chances to win in the future.

D.4.3 Tournament 3

The agents submitted to tournament 3 were just a test of the submission process for a member of the team that had not yet submitted a container to the tournament.

D.4.4 Tournament 4

In preparation for tournament 4, we made further adjustments from tournament 2 by adding noise to the winning rate payoffs. The reason why we make such adjustment is that rewards as payoffs does not quite fit into the context. It is hard to get access to the pelican reward when panther is the driving agent, and there is no clear definition on how to define the rewards if the pelican is not the driving agent. Hence, we test out a new solution to see whether it works better. The parameters of our model training are not different from tournament 2, except for the value of payoffs.

D.4.5 Tournament 5

In preparation for tournament 5, we tested out our theorem on sensitivity analysis under 28x26 board configuration. We first trained a set of 23 models (both pelican and panther) using the configurations from our sensitivity analysis, i.e. train the models on configurations based on the most sensitive parameters. We then used these models as the initial models for a run of PNM using the provided tournament configuration. We kept adding random noise to avoid early termination. We added more tests on PPO optimized parameters and the impact of observation normalization. Since we have quite a lot of initial models, the evaluation process ran slowly, so that we only trained for two iterations.

D.5 Findings and limitations

D.5.1 Schedule of reward shaping environments

The `PlarkEnvSparse` environment provides the sparse reward for the end conditions for both players. The `PlarkEnv` environment rewards the end conditions and penalises illegal actions for both players; it rewards the pelican for dropping a sonobuoy or penalises if it was within the range of an existing sonobuoy. The `PantherEnvReachTop` environment rewards the panther for moving north and penalises the panther for moving south; it also rewards for the panther escaping but not for other end conditions. The `PlarkEnvGuidedReward` environment rewards the pelican if it moves closer to the panther; it did not provide a reward for end conditions. The

`PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeployment` environment rewards the pelican if it drops a sonobuoy; however, the reward would be less if it was dropped within the range of an existing sonobuoy; it did not provide a reward for end conditions. The `PlarkEnvIllegalMove` environment rewards not making an illegal move; it did not provide a reward for the end conditions.

The custom `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeploymentIllegalMove` environment provides the same rewards as `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeployment` except it also penalises illegal moves. The custom `PelicanEnvParam` environment rewards the end conditions; it penalises making an illegal move; it rewards dropping a sonobuoy; however, the reward would be less if it was dropped within the range of an existing sonobuoy; it penalises ending the turn if it still had sonobuoys to drop or if there were *hot* (active) sonobuoys and no torpedoes in the water; it also penalises dropping torpedoes outside of the range of hot sonobuoys.

Our first attempted environment schedule used the 10x10 balanced game configuration; the panther schedule used `PantherEnvReachTop`, `PlarkEnv`, `PantherEnvReachTop`, and then repeated `PlarkEnv` for a total of 12 stages; the pelican schedule used `PlarkEnvGuidedReward`, `PlarkEnvGuidedReward`, `PlarkEnv`, `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeployment`, `PlarkEnvIllegalMove`, and then repeated `PlarkEnv` for a total of 12 stages. For the panther, the motivation of this schedule was to achieve the escape win condition, while still allowing opportunity for it to find the other win conditions. For the pelican, the motivation was to use the guided reward, which leaks information about the panther location, to teach about the starting location and movement of the panther. We found that the pelican overused torpedoes with minimal use of sonobuoys, as during the initial stages of training this approach was able to achieve good win rates due to the leaking of panther location.

In order to address this deficiency, we adjusted the pelican environment schedule to use the `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeployment` on stages 1,6,10,12; the `PlarkEnvGuidedReward` on stages 4,7; the `PlarkEnv` on the remaining stages up to 21. For the panther schedule, we used the `PantherEnvReachTop` on stages 1,5,8,11,14; the `PlarkEnv` on the remaining stages up to 21. We used the 25×25 game configuration that was used for the Friday tournament. Due to a flaw in the `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeployment` reward function, where it would reward an

illegal attempt to drop a sonobuoy on top of an existing one, the pelican learnt to just sit in the same place, repeatedly dropping sonobuoys in the same location; this behaviour was evident after the first stage, but was not unlearned even with nine stages of `PlarkEnv` at the end of training.

In order to address this deficiency, we adjusted the pelican environment schedule to use the `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeploymentIllegalMove` instead of the `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeployment`. We also adjust the panther environment schedule to use the `PantherEnvReachTop` on all odd numbered stages up to stage 17 and the `PlarkEnv` on the remaining stages. To improve the training time, this was performed on the 10×10 balanced game configuration. We found that this achieved a reasonable spacing of the sonobuoys. However, due to the game configuration, the pelican was often able to drop a torpedo on the panther within two turns by immediately moving to the starting area of the panther; thus, the use of sonobuoys was not useful in actually achieving the victory. This is illustrated in Figure 50.

Figure 50: Distribution of sonobuoys with schedule focussed on `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeploymentIllegalMove`.

The same environment schedule was tested on the 20 balanced configuration, in order to avoid the easy win by pelican. Since we found the panther training times were significantly longer than the pelican and since the pelican behaviour was of more interest since it was typically harder to learn, we ran an additional test which only trained the panther on stages 1,2,7,8,12,16,20,21 and skipped panther training on the remain

stages. Both of these performed similarly, with only one or two sonobuoys being deployed. A similar behaviour was observed with the 10×10 tournament configuration, which used a lower pelican move per turn limit which similarly avoided the easy win by pelican. For this game configuration, however, we also replace most uses of `PlarkEnv` with `PlarkEnvSparse`.

In these configurations without an easy win for the pelican, the `PlarkEnvSonobuoyDeployment*` environments did not sufficiently encourage the use of sonobuoys. So, we moved to a schedule which used the `PelicanEnvParam`, which penalised ending turn if it was possible to drop sonobuoys, to provide a strong signal that the sonobuoys should be utilised as quickly as possible. We tested two versions of this environment, the first did not include the penalty for dropping torpedoes outside the range of hot sonobuoys while the second did include this component. For the panther schedule, we used `PantherEnvReachTop` for stage 1 and `PlarkEnvSparse` for stages 2,8,16,18-21, with the remaining stages skipping training. For the pelican schedule, we used `PelicanEnvParam` for stages 1,2,4,5,7,10,12 and `PlarkEnvSparse` for the remaining stages up to 21. We used both a 10×10 and 28×28 game configuration for both versions of the `PelicanEnvParam`. All four variations demonstrated an improvement in sonobuoy layout. As expected, the 10×10 configuration was easier to learn; for the 28×28 configuration, the movement was less efficient and also resulted in less coverage of the space. These results are illustrates in Figure 51.

D.5.2 Sensitivity analysis

The `SALib sobol.analyze` function outputs an S_i matrix that contains first order, totalled and second order sensitivities, and their confidence interval level (at the 0.95 default)[54]. This function was used to analyse the victory proportion of the pelican and the panther in turn.

The confidence values are all quite large - they average 0.257 for the pelican and 0.353 for the panther, on the second-order sensitivities. This is likely due to the comparatively small number of samples and the large parameter space.

Pelican First order (greater than or equal to the average, discounting negative values):

- map height (0.265)
- torpedos (0.200)
- sonobuoys (0.113)

Second order (greater than or equal to the average, discounting negative values):

- sonobuoys-torpedo search range (0.083)
- torpedo search range-sonobuoy active range (0.079)
- torpedo turns-sonobuoy active range (0.074)

Totals:

- torpedo speed (0.719)
- torpedos (0.693)
- map width (0.631)
- map height (0.619)
- sonobuoy active range (0.597)
- torpedo search range (0.580)
- moves pelican (0.579)
- torpedo turns (0.551)
- moves panther (0.537)
- sonobuoys (0.473)
- turns (0.348)

Suggest: varying the top 4 totalled sensitivity parameters, torpedo speed, number of torpedos, map width, map height, and the number of sonobuoys, such that all the strongest first order effects are included. The second order effects are small enough to be discounted.

Panther First order (greater than or equal to the average, discounting negative values):

- map height (0.182)
- torpedos (0.097)

Second order (greater than or equal to the average, discounting negative values):

- torpedo search range-sonobuoy active range (0.488)
- height-sonobuoy active range (0.465)
- torpedo speed-sonobuoy active range (0.401)
- moves pelican-sonobuoys (0.361)

- sonobuoys-sonobuoy active range (0.326)
- torpedo speed-torpedo search range (0.292)
- sonobuoys-torpedo turns (0.291)
- torpedos-sonobuoys (0.287)
- sonobuoys-torpedo speed (0.273)
- turns-sonobuoys (0.267)
- moves pelican-sonobuoy active range (0.267)
- moves panther-torpedo speed (0.26)
- moves pelican-torpedo speed (0.251)
- moves pelican-torpedo search (0.251)
- torpedos-torpedo search range (0.25)
- height-torpedo search (0.23)
- moves panther-sonobuoy active range (0.223)
- moves panther-sonobuoys (0.205)
- sonobuoys-torpedo search range (0.198)
- torpedos-sonobuoy active range (0.193)
- turns-sonobuoy active range (0.19)
- moves pelican-torpedos (0.177)
- moves pelican-torpedo turns (0.177)

Totals:

- torpedos (1.122)
- sonobuoy active (0.958)
- torpedo search (0.947)
- sonobuoys (0.926)
- map height (0.763)

- moves panther (0.754)
- torpedo speed (0.745)
- map width (0.745)
- turns (0.717)
- moves pelican (0.708)
- torpedo turns (0.570)

Suggest: varying the number of torpedos, the number of sonobuoys and top 2 second-order pairs, that is, torpedo search range - sonobuoy active range, and map height - sonobuoy active range.

Results of the stress testing analysis We performed a stress test on a set of chosen parameters. Below, in table 20, we present the cross-sensitivities for the main results. As expected the board size is the variable with more effect on the policy's performance.

Table 20: Cross-sensitivities to board size and game’s configuration parameters. Stress-test approach.

Board Size	Variable	Pelican	Panther
		Change in Avg Reward	Change in Avg Reward
10x10	baseline	0%	0%
25x25	board alone	-118%	-347%
25x25	maximum_turns	-115%	-259%
25x25	pan_move_limit	-214%	-327%
25x25	pel_move_limit	-163%	-356%
25x25	default_torps	-151%	-346%
25x25	turn_limit	-123%	-343%
25x25	search_range	-175%	-351%
25x25	default_sonobuoys	-172%	-354%
30x30	board alone	-87%	-357%
30x30	maximum_turns	-180%	-343%
30x30	pan_move_limit	-154%	-355%
30x30	pel_move_limit	-199%	-358%
30x30	default_torps	-214%	-353%
30x30	turn_limit	-230%	-356%
30x30	search_range	-151%	-357%
30x30	default_sonobuoys	-184%	-354%
35x35	board alone	-178%	-348%
35x35	maximum_turns	-119%	-352%
35x35	pan_move_limit	-133%	-355%
35x35	pel_move_limit	-238%	-357%
35x35	default_torps	-294%	-331%
35x35	turn_limit	-62%	-345%
35x35	search_range	-18%	-356%
35x35	default_sonobuoys	-115%	-350%

D.5.3 Variation

The mean victory proportions across the 100 runs with `num_trials` set to 10 were 0.181 and 0.819 for the pelican and the panther respectively. The standard deviations were calculated as 0.126 and 0.122 - proportionally huge for the pelican, and still quite big for the panther! These values can also be compared with the 3 values measured over 1000 runs given in table 21. The fact that even these values have a standard deviation of 0.011 and 0.013 (small but non-negligible) shows that the variation is significant.

X_{1000}	pelican	panther
run 1	0.172	0.817
run 2	0.147	0.849
run 3	0.168	0.836

Table 21: Victory proportions measured over 1000 runs

The averages of the Δ values calculated as per equation 1 using the 3 1000-run values give an idea of the deviation from a “true” value of victory proportion. These are presented in table 22. The highest value here, of 0.708, shows that the mean deviation with respect to the second 1000-run value is 71%!

Δ	pelican	panther
run 1	0.590	0.124
run 2	0.708	0.127
run 3	0.607	0.126

Table 22: Mean deviation of victory proportions measured over 100 runs with respect to each of the 1000-run values given in table 21

Shown in figure 52 are the mean victory proportions for the pelican and the panther calculated using the

`helper.check_victory(model, env, num_trials)` with `num_trials` set to different values between 10 and 200. This function was called 20 times for each value for the number of evaluation episodes, to allow the calculation. As can be seen, the change in the mean value seems to level off around 100 evaluation episodes.

D.6 Future work and research avenues

There are 4 avenues that have been begun during this DSG, but which were not completed or could be improved with additional time.

Pelican training: Whilst training the pelican using reward shaping, it was seen that the agent was over-fitting to the panther’s behaviour, eg by pre-emptively dropping a torpedo where it expected the panther to be. In order

to avoid this, the pelican should be trained using multiple diverse panther policies.

Sensitivity analysis: Given the results presented in section D.5.3, that the accuracy of the `helper.check_victory(model,env,num_trials)` degraded as the value of `num_trials` decreased, it is unlikely that the sensitivity analysis results are accurate. This assumption is supported by the large confidence intervals given by the `sobol.analyze(dict, outputs)` method. It would therefore be sensible to re-run the script with many more evaluation episodes, and possibly more sampled parameter sets.

Curriculum learning: Thus far, to establish a training schedule with incremental increases in difficulty for the agents, only the provided configurations have been used. It is not known whether these are in fact the best stages of training. It would be interesting to instead use the results from the sensitivity analysis, or the “bump and re-eval” process, to guide or even automatically form a training schedule.

Initial PNM agents: So far, each PNM training run for the tournaments has involved taking the best models from the previous PNM run to use as initial agents. Are there better candidates? For instance, agents trained through reward shaping, or using a training schedule (as described above)? Or even “expert” agents trained on the configurations based on the sensitivity analysis.

D.7 Team members

Kirsten Richardson is a second-year PhD student at Newcastle University within the School of Computer Science. Her position falls under the Cloud Computing for Big Data Centre for Doctoral Training, however her research is machine-learning based, specifically deep reinforcement learning, with a project that looks at using deep RL for active object tracking in the context of marine mammal conservation. Her role on the DSG team has been group facilitator.

Stephanie Ford is a radar scientist in the Sensing Group of Dstl. She is completing a part-time PhD in cognitive radar mode selection at UCL. The understanding of cognition as continually learning how to adapt to the environment suggests the use of AI such as deep RL, which is where the focus of the project has settled. During the data study group, she has investigated the sensitivity of the agents' performance to the game configurations.

Joel Bosveld is an analyst for the Department of Defence in the Defence Science and Technology Group. He was a research associate with the ARC Centre of Excellence in Gravitational Wave Discovery (OzGrav). He completed a PhD at the University of Western Australia within the School of Mathematics and Statistics and the School of Computer Science and Software Engineering. His contribution to the DSG team has been to investigate reward shaping.

Leyang Xue is a first-year PhD student at University of Edinburgh School of Informatics. His research focus falls generally into the category of edge computing. AI, especially deep learning and RL, has emerging applications in edge computing, typically network route control and traffic engineering. His role in the group has been investigating hyper-parameter tuning and targeting transferability by mixing policies.

Lucia Cipolina-Kun is a PHD candidate at the department of Electrical and Electronical Engineering, University of Bristol. Her research focuses on the application of deep RL for traffic orchestration in a mixed autonomy setting. Her role in the group has been the study of the sensitivity-based approach.

Qingbiao Li is a third year PhD Student from the Department of Computer Science and Technology at University of Cambridge supervised by Dr Amanda Prorok. During his PhD, his focus is on communication-aware motion planning for multi-robot coordination. He is investigating Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) how to build communication channels for multi-agent and multi-robot systems so that they can learn how to communicate between each other explicitly. His role in the group has been investigating hyper-parameter optimisation, domain adaptation for multi-stage training.

a: 10×10 ,
without torpedo drop component

b: 28×28 ,
without torpedo drop component

c: 28×28 ,
with torpedo drop component

d: 10×10 ,
with torpedo drop component

Figure 51: Distribution of sonobuoys with schedule focussed on PelicanEnvParam.

Figure 52: Mean and variance of the calculated victory proportions for the pelican (left) and panther (right) with different numbers of evaluation episodes

E Robust Adversarial Approaches

During the study group, the PIs also experimented with some strategies, which we describe here.

An increasingly popular approach for curriculum learning is to use autonomous progression functions to determine the complexity of the task with which an agent is confronted based on their current performance [3]. Meanwhile robust adversarial reinforcement learning (RARL) approaches are increasingly also being viewed as a form of curriculum learning [11]. In RARL a domain agent learns to perturb/modify the environment to increase the challenge of the task faced by the domain’s protagonist, e.g., though applying forces to the centre of gravity while the protagonist attempts to solve a task such as the InvertedPendulum [49]. In RARL the domain agent receives the negative reward of the protagonist, and is therefore incentivised to take actions that make the domain as challenging as possible for the protagonist. However, similar to curriculum learning – where a sub-optimal fixed progression function can be detrimental to learning [3] – the magnitude of the forces available to the domain adversary often require moderation. Indeed, there is a danger that the adversaries’ manipulations can make the domain unsolvable for the protagonist.

Recently Dennis et al. [11] proposed an extension to the RARL framework that incentivises the domain adversary to ensure that protagonists can reach their objectives. Protagonist Antagonist Induced Regret Environment Design (PAIRED) adds an *antagonist* to the RARL framework, which shares the same properties as the protagonist. The domain agent’s objective is to maximise the regret – the difference between the reward obtained by the antagonist $U(\pi^A)$ and that obtained by the protagonist $U(\pi^P)$:

$$REGRET(\pi^A, \pi^P) = U(\pi^A) - U(\pi^P) \quad (2)$$

PAIRED attempts to find increasingly sophisticated ways to exploit differences between the two agents’ policies and make the domain more challenging for the protagonist. As a result PAIRED can be viewed as a form of multivariate-curriculum learning.

E.1 Implementation

We conduct a preliminary investigation to investigate the extent to which PAIRED can be used to modify domain parameterisations within the PLARK domain along separate parameter axis. We focused our evaluation on the training of the pelican. To encourage the deployment of sonobuoys the pelican is only given *one* torpedo per episode. For our experiments the adversary is given the opportunity to modify one out of two domain configurations at the beginning of each episode, namely: i.) The initial distance between the panther and the pelican with respect to the y-axis (the start positions with respect to the x-axis was chosen uniformly); ii.) the search range of the torpedo. The adversary’s action space consists of increasing/decreasing the y-distance ($[8, 25]$) and search ranges ($[2, 5]$) respectively. The domain agent is implemented with tabular-Q, using ϵ -greedy exploration with a fixed $\epsilon = 0.2$ and learning rate $\alpha = 0.1$. The protagonist and antagonists are implemented with PPO. We compare PAIRED against RARL (without giving any restrictions to the adversary), and gather 8 runs per setting. The experiments take place in a 25x25 grid setting, sonobuoy active range is set to 4, and we use *Panther Agent Random Walk* as an opponent.

E.2 Results

For our evaluation we compare the two approaches with respect to the proportion of victories (Sub-Figure 53a) for the three types of agents (RARL-Protagonist, PAIRED-Protagonist and PAIRED-Antagonist), the starting distance (Sub-Figure 53b) and the search range (Sub-Figure 53c). Interestingly despite the both adversaries seemingly making similar modifications to the search ranges and starting distances (on average), there are significant differences in the proportions of victories when comparing RARL to PAIRED. Our initial assumption was that RARL would simply learn to increase the starting-distance (and decrease the search range). However, upon closer inspection we only observe one run where this was indeed the case with respect to the starting distance. This indicates that the RARL adversary is finding subtle ways to make the task challenging for the protagonist, which is something that requires further investigations. If the results are indeed due to subtle attacks, then this finding could also provide interesting insights for the

Figure 53: Comparison of Protagonist Antagonist Induced Regret Environment Design (PAIRED) vs Robust Adversarial Reinforcement Learning for training the Pelican within a 25x25 PLARK domain. A learning domain adversary was given the opportunity to modify the starting distance between panther and pelican and the torpedo search range prior to each episode.

development of automated progression functions for curriculum learning.

We observe in Sub-Figure 53a that the percentage of victories for the antagonist are higher on average compared to those of the protagonist. Naturally, given the small sample size a logical next step would be to verify this result through gather a large number of additional runs. Finally, we note that the victory proportions in Sub-Figure 53a need to be viewed through the lens of the starting distance and search ranges form Sub-Figures 53b and 53c respectively.

E.3 Future Work

The above results raise some interesting questions for future research. First, we would like to establish how the RARL adversary is overpowering the protagonist in this simple setting. In addition, we plan to: i.) Add further parameters that the adversary can tune; ii.) Evaluate the robustness of the protagonist (and antagonist) policies towards unseen domain parameterisations and new opponents; iii.) Apply PAIRED and RARL to competitive reinforcement learning, by training both the pelican and the panther; and iv.) Conducting a comparison to autonomous online progression functions [3].

F Tournament Results

In this section we present the results of the daily tournaments held throughout the second half of the two-week DSG. The domain parameters, apart from the starting positions of the two agents, used for each tournament are given at the start of the subsections in this section, each followed by a plot of the tournament results. The starting positions of the two agents were allowed to vary across tournament matches within the following map-size dependent ranges:

- `start_row_panther` in $[0.8 * \text{map_height}, \text{map_height}-1]$
- `start_col_panther` in $[0.33 * \text{map_width}, 0.66 * \text{map_width}]$
- `start_row_pelican` in $[0, 0.2 * \text{map_height}]$
- `start_col_pelican` in $[0, 0.33 * \text{map_width}]$

How to read the tournament results plots. Each plot is a table of sub-plots with rows corresponding to different pelican agents and columns corresponding to panther agents. The rows and columns are labelled with the team name and agent name, where we have:

- Transferability 1 \implies Team 1
- Transferability 2 \implies Team 2
- Robustness 1 \implies Team 3
- Robustness 2 \implies Team 4
- PI team \implies Team Test

Each subplot has two bars, the left red bar shows the number of wins for the panther and the right green bar shows the number of wins for the pelican. From the Monday tournament onward, to save time we did not run two agents from the same team against each other, and such pairings show up in the tables as subplots.

The PI team submitted the following set of rule-based agents from the Monday tournament onward:

- `panther_random_walk`,

- panther_agent_rand_opportunistic,
- panther_agent_move_north,
- pelican_agent_top_third_buoys,
- pelican_agent_half_grid_buoys,
- pelican_agent_bottom_third_buoys,
- pelican_agent_any_size.

Additionally, the PI team submitted:

- a pelican agent `pelican_james_ea`, which was trained with an evolutionary algorithm against `panther_agent_move_north`;
- a pelican agent, `pelican_rahul_10x10`, and a panther agent, `panther_rahul_10x10`, which were trained using PNM with an initial population of agents that were best responses against the above-mentioned rule-based agents.

F.1 Friday 5th March

Figure 54: Domain parameters: map_width=10; map_height=10; max_turns=50; move_limit_panther=1; move_limit_pelican=25; default_torpedos=5; default_sonobuoys=25; turn_limit=3; torpedo_speed=4; torpedo_search_range=4; torpedo_active_range=4.

Figure 55: Domain parameters: map_width=25; map_height=25; max_turns=50; move_limit_panther=1; move_limit_pelican=25; default_torpedos=5; default_sonobuoys=25; turn_limit=3; torpedo_speed=4; torpedo_search_range=4; torpedo_active_range=4.

F.2 Monday 8th March

Figure 56: Domain parameters: map_width=26; map_height=33; max_turns=50; move_limit_panther=2; move_limit_pelican=15; default_torpedos=5; default_sonobuoys=25; turn_limit=3; torpedo_speed=4; torpedo_search_range=3; torpedo_active_range=4.

F.3 Tuesday 9th March

Figure 57: Domain parameters: map_width=10; map_height=10; max_turns=25; move_limit_panther=1; move_limit_pelican=5; default_torpedos=2; default_sonobuoys=15; turn_limit=2; torpedo_speed=2; torpedo_search_range=3; torpedo_active_range=2.

Figure 58: Domain parameters: map_width=28; map_height=26; max_turns=43; move_limit_panther=1; move_limit_pelican=19; default_torpedos=1; default_sonobuoys=25; turn_limit=3; torpedo_speed=4; torpedo_search_range=3; torpedo_active_range=1.

Figure 60: Domain Parameters: map_width=28; map_height=28; max_turns=25; move_limit_panther=3; move_limit_pelican=18; default_torpedos=2; default_sonobuoys=21; turn_limit=3; torpedo_speed=2; torpedo_search_range=4; torpedo_active_range=3.

F.5 Thursday 11th March

Figure 61: Domain parameters: map_width=10; map_height=10; max_turns=31; move_limit_panther=3; move_limit_pelican=5; default_torpedos=1; default_sonobuoys=15; turn_limit=2; torpedo_speed=2; torpedo_search_range=3; torpedo_active_range=2.

Figure 62: Domain parameters: map_width=28; map_height=25; max_turns=30; move_limit_panther=2; move_limit_pelican=17; default_torpedos=3; default_sonobuoys=21; turn_limit=3; torpedo_speed=2; torpedo_search_range=3; torpedo_active_range=2.

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